

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D4.1 Use Cases' field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	951867	Acronym	5G-ROUTES
Full Title	5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials		
Start Date	01/09/2020	Duration	54 months
Project URL	https://www.5g-routes.eu		
Deliverable	D4.1 Use Cases' field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook		
Work Package	WP4 Large-scale cross-border CAM field trials		
Contractual due date	28.2.2022	Actual submission date	21.10.2024
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Beneficiary	BRA		
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
V1.1	24/02/2023	100%	Updated version based on EC reviewers' comments and suggestions	BRA
V1.2	25/03/2023	100%	Update on clustering focus and experimental cycles planning	BRA
V1.3	07/04/2023	100%	Update of experimental scenarios tables from the UC owners	ALL
V1.4	04/12/2023	90%	Redesign of structure to better describe the methodology steps	BRA
V1.5	11/12/2023	92%	Added timelines for every Eco-system	BRA
V1.6	18/12/2023	93%	Changes in the structure due to partners suggestion.	BRA
V1.7	15/01/2024	95%	Improvements in Trials sites description sections thanks to technical partners observations.	BRA
V1.8	31/01/2024	100%	Update of experimental scenarios tables from the UC owners due to Eco-systems organisation.	ALL
V1.9	19/02/2024	100%	Internal reviewers' comments and suggestions	EEE, TTU
V2.0	22/02/2024	100%	Improvements based on the internal review	BRA
V2.1	21/03/2024	100%	Improvements based on Deliverable defence	BRA, VTT, TTU
V2.2	16/09/2024	100%	Improvements based on reviewers' suggestions	BRA
V2.3	01/10/2024	100%	Test Case Tables update and inclusion in the Document (Annex I and II)	BRA, UC Owners
V2.4	11/10/2024	100%	Improvements after review	BRA

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AR	Augmented reality
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth generation wireless technology
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
API	Application Programming Interface
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility
E2E	End-to- End
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
HW	Hardware
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector
KPI	Key performance indicator
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NSA	Non stand-alone 5G technology
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
SA	Stand-alone 5G technology

SLA	Service Level Agreement
SUT	System under test
SW	Software
TaaS	Testing as a service
UCCs	Use Case Categories
UCs	Use Cases
URLCC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V&V	Verification and validation
VR	Virtual reality
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of cutting-edge cooperative connected and automated mobility (CCAM) systems and the 5G uninterrupted coverage and services along a defined 5G cross-border corridor (Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki), spanning across 3 European Union (EU) member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland). These trials aim to validate the latest 5G capabilities and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions. The goal is to speed up the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable connected and automated mobility (CAM) ecosystems and services in digitised motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

This document sets out the foundation for the methodologies to approach testing across the different pilot sites and use cases during the trials. It combines the work carried in **task 4.1. “Planning, setup and operational management”** which concentrates on the approach to derive scenarios details from the use case and providing the test-bench to the stakeholders involved. This enables the demonstration, through field trials, that the latest 3GPP releases in 5G infrastructure support services continuity solutions and the key performance indicator (KPI) requirements needed for delivering innovative CCAM services that require 5G performance capabilities during cross-border situations.

This approach will define the different templates and formats for the formalisation, specification of the scenarios, test objectives and related test cases while setting out the basis for the different key concepts, entities and the testing process for the lifetime of the project. Finally, it will detail the **procedures to optimise the planning and execution of the different use cases** by aligning and chaining the work carried out during the lab trials and the activities to conduct field trials.

In this deliverable, our aim is to **establish the groundwork for a unified testing framework**. Starting by developing a single approach for the report formats and the technological validation. Thus, paving the way for the validation of the solutions deployed for the 5G-ROUTES project in the considered environments: Terrestrial and Maritime.

2 Introduction

The primary objective of this document is to establish and evaluate the methodologies for testing, validating, and benchmarking the results of the technological validation for use cases. We will outline our strategy to achieve this objective by addressing the following questions from a technological validation and test report format perspective:

What framework can we provide to approach the testing of the different use case categories (UCC) and use cases (UC) within each of those categories?

- How can we review and analyse what needs to be verified and validated?
- How can we translate the requirements into an executable format to support both test execution and the measurements involved?
- What kind of test reports can we design to provide genuine insight into the results, as well as to enable and support the project's objectives (5G Routes – H2020, n.d.).
- What process can we define that would fit neatly into the project's iterative agile process?

Although the comprehensive process for gathering detailed use-case scenarios, including their relevant KPIs and test bed requirements is covered in D1.2 "Use cases, scenarios, specifications and target KPIs for 5G for CAM final version", it can be used as a starting point to define our methodologies. The description of reference validation frameworks inspired from other 5G research programs are also presented.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal deliverable and task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA deliverable & tasks Descriptions.

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.1 Definition and detailed analysis of CAM use cases, scenarios, specifications for technological enablers and target KPIs (technological and business)	This task captures the requirements from the end-user CCAM stakeholders, including the articulation of detailed use case scenarios and usability needs, and relevant target technological and business KPIs, which will be validated in the field trials. This task is divided into two key sub tasks: (a) systematic compilation of current use cases features and capabilities (b) requirements analysis.	D1.1 Chapter 3	The systematic compilation of current use cases features, and capabilities is done in chapter 3 The requirement analysis, including end users' needs, will lead to the definition of the test facilities, test scenarios and KPIs (subtask b)
		D1.2 chapter 2	Definition of the methodology and selection of technical KPIs

	<p>Integrated satellite/terrestrial architectures and interfaces between traffic flow from satellite operator and MNO core network will also be defined in this task.</p> <p>A requirement capture will involve the documentation of CCAM end-users needs and opinions about new innovative use cases that require 5G performance capabilities in the domains of automotive, railways, transport & logistics, IoT and infotainment.</p> <p>Such use cases will be mapped to specific target KPI and SLA values (e.g. throughput, mobility, latency, density, reliability, positioning accuracy, coverage, service provisioning time, QoS, QoE, etc.), which will set the baseline for conducting the actual measurements during the field trials.</p>	D1.2 chapter 3	<p>Definition of test scenarios. The continuous review of this document will lead to a constant update of the UCs and their needs for the testing phase.</p>
T1.2 CAM deployment plan and long-term strategies for full scale deployment of 5G infrastructure	<p>The deployment plan will define the timeline that all the experimental cycles will adopt. Starting from a NSA Eco-system for the first cycle then the following cycles will take into consideration the specifications and time steps of the deployment of the final SA 5G infrastructure.</p>	D1.3 chapter 7	<p>The timeline, updated in the next deliverable drop, will be considered in the experiments planning to align them with their requirements in terms of infrastructure and the deployment of the required equipment in the trials sites.</p>
T1.4 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	<p>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management. In particular, as far as the technological validation is concerned, we will define the procedures for collecting the data feeds from the 5G nodes, stating also how these feeds will be used and analysed by the Tenant Web Portal to produce and present the KPI values in a graphical form. Threshold limits for the benchmarking of the results will also be defined per target KPI based</p>	D1.8 chapter 3	<p>Overview of the testing framework, KPIs and data collection, and concept definition for the technological performance assessment framework.</p>
		D1.8 chapter 4	<p>Data collection for the technological performance assessment.</p>
		D1.8 chapter 7	<p>Specific aspects per use case and use case category.</p>

	on the requirements stemming from each CAM use case.		
T2.4 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment	the updated version of the TWP will be deployed and used for the large-scale cross-border field trials execution, enabling UC owners to conduct tests in the field under various scenarios, visualize KPI measurements, and validate testing results.	D2.8	The connection between the tests and how to report their results in the tenant Web portal.
T2.5 integration and testing of technological Enablers	contributes to the integration, deployment, validation, and testing of the CAM Services Platform by creating a strategy and implementation methodology. It ensures that WP2 outcomes are developed to a high standard and can be executed and integrated compatibly with the field trial infrastructure.	D2.9	The constant development and upgrade of the technological enablers will be connected to the configuration of the tests of the different use case categories.
T3.1 Installation, setup and configuration of 5G infrastructure including seamless integration between terrestrial and satellite 5G	This task focuses on the preparation and configuration of the different trials sites considered in the project with special attention on satellite fall back solutions.	D3.1	Describe the trials sites features and how the network has been deployed at several locations where different experimental phases will be carried out.
T3.4 Lab trials and operational readiness for large scale field trials	resume highlights experience in deploying and testing 5G enablers and use cases, emphasizing skills in deployment, integration, and testing in preparation for field trials.	D3.10	The results obtained from the lab trials and the operational readiness for field trials will be based on the verification activities reported in this deliverable.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This document outlines the methodologies applied for the organisation, planning and deployment of the different experimental phases of the unique experimental cycle that will be carried out during the final period of 5GRoutes project. Due to a redefinition of the objectives in terms of infrastructure requirements and the planification of the related tests and experiments, the different innovative services and connected technologies

will be deployed and tested in a stand-alone 5G technology (SA) Eco-system after the adjustments carried out in the previously realised lab trials.

The main structure of the document is organised as follows:

- 1 **Section 3** review the methodologies already applied in the project and previously reported in deliverables from previous work packages giving an overall view about: the technological validation, the test reports and their relationships.
- 2 **Section 4** is mainly dedicated to task 4.1 “Planning, setup & operational management for the test reports format” as well as part of task 4.2 “Large-scale cross-border field trials execution” and task 4.3 “Performance evaluation and lessons learned”. We kick off the technical validation process by presenting the first version of the solution for both methodologies: the test reports and the technical validation with a focus on the initial activities to be carried out along with the necessary templates for task 4.2. The technological validation methodology also covers the adaptation and analysis of possible validation frameworks inspired from ETSI and other 5G research programs (5G-SOLUTIONS, 5G-TOURS, 5G-EVE, 5G-MOBIX, 5G-TANGO, 5G-VINNI, TRIANGLE, 5G-GENESIS). From an overall perspective, the methodology encompasses analysis of the foundations; including terminology, concepts, definition and elaboration of methodology that encompasses the testing regime.
- 3 **Section 5** reports in detail the plan related to the different experimental Eco-system (terrestrial and maritime) involved in the validation activities, focusing on the locations, facilities, logistics and timeline. The section report information about the locations related 5G infrastructure implementation for the field trials.
- 4 **Section 6, 7 & 8** contributes with a sample of the use case descriptions, contributed by the UCs owners and gathered as an entry criterion for the next task. Furthermore, the test procedures are introduced, as well as their execution in terms of testing concepts and reporting.
- 5 **Section 9 & 10** then concludes a summary and the future work.

2.3 Linkage to other project outputs

Task 4.1 collects the outputs from previous and concurrent activities that aim to prepare the field for the experimentation of the innovative CCAM of the project. The first work package (WP) of the project provided a detailed and comprehensive definition of the use cases (UCs) and their relationship within UCs categories (UCCs), establishing common paths for the infrastructure preparation across different groups of use cases.

However, due to the project refocus, a set of use cases has been removed and the UCs categories have been replaced with a new form of classification based on the objectives of the use cases. The new classification methodology grouped the UCs, facilitating the organisation of their experiments and consequently demonstrations through the different physical environments. This new method of identifying the groups has been named as “Eco-systems”, producing two different, maritime and terrestrial.

This bundling method has not influenced the UCs development and maintained the requirements in terms of technological enablers needs and their integration. This approach collected the requirements, which, considered in WP2, supported the development of the required technological enablers and infrastructure settings to support the wide spectrum of different services involved for the UCCs. WP3 provided the first approximation to the setup of the lab trials needed to configure, for the first time, all the systems involved and their adjustments in simplified settings to first run the different UCs.

WP4 and especially Task 4.1 are the point where all the previous efforts and developments are summed to deploy the UCs on the field and carry out their validation.

This document provides an advanced definition of the experiments related to every use case, within its category, through the description of the different experimental scenarios that each use case will carry out to adjust and refine all the conditions, infrastructures, tools and systems to set up and experiment the CCAM in the first simplified phases and finally in the most complex real cross border experiments in the different eco-systems.

The approximation to the UCs experiments, their detailed requirements and their specific needs in terms of operations required to set up and run the UCs trials on field has been reviewed and updated during the Lab trials experimental phase. The obtained updates are the result of the modifications carried out in WP2 and WP3 because of their direct relationship within the project and their implication in the field trials experimental phase of the UCs and the related CCAM carried out in WP4.

Table 2: Document linkage with other deliverables.

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Contribution and Value of linkage
D1.2 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM	The UCs and their needs for the testing phase, first described in D1.1 and D1.9, have been updated.
D1.11 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM	The update of these methodologies will be implemented in the experimental phase.
D1.8 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	The testing framework, first described in D1.7 and D1.12, has been updated to consider the validation methodologies.
D2.7 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment	The connection between the tests and how to report their results in the tenant Web portal.
D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological Enablers	The constant development and upgrade of the technological enablers will be connected to the configuration of the tests of the different use case categories.
D3.1 Report on 5G Infrastructure setup for CAM	The continuous improvements on the configuration of the trials sites have been resumed and reported in this document.
D3.8. Report on results of the lab trials and of the operational readiness for field trials v1.0	The results obtained from the lab trails and the operational readiness for field trials will be based on the plan for field trials described in this deliverable.

2.4 Reviewers' comments and suggestion for the Resubmission

This document is being resubmitted after its first delivery attempt in Spring 2022. Reviewers' comments (table below) have been considered and the document has been completely restructured and changed to fulfil with the suggestions provided by the reviewers during their first review.

Table 3: Second submission Reviewers' comments.

Rejection topic	Answer/document modifications
This is the first submission of the deliverable that deals with the planning of use cases and trials. It describes the testing methodology to be used in 5G-ROUTES. The methodology is first described in a generic way and then how it is going to be applied in the context of 5G-ROUTES. The proposed methodology is appropriate for the project objectives.	We simplified the methodology sections mentioning the methodology already described in the already published technical deliverables.
Additionally, the document defines the terminology to be used to describe testing-related concepts and the naming conventions for the use case descriptions, results, etc. In the annex, the scenarios of each use case are also presented according to the proposed template and naming conventions.	We understand that this part was fine assessed. For this reason, we just adjusted the naming conventions to the introduced Eco-System.
This Follow-up document contains a repetition of some information already found in other deliverables. At the same time, it uses a different approach for the "testing framework" compared to the explanation of other deliverables. It is not clear what level of interoperability, communication and integration is going to happen between the partners that have written the other deliverables.	The "testing framework" has been harmonized with the other deliverables where the testing methodology is presented.
On the other hand, this deliverable claim to use the methodology from the 5G VINNI project as opposed to the 5G-SOLUTIONS mentioned in other deliverables. How does this then fit the rest of the testing framework, and the experimental Eco-system described in other deliverables?	We reviewed the document and refocused the described methodology to the one proper of the more referenced (along 5G-ROUTES project) project 5G-SOLUTIONS.
Rejection topic (June 24)	Answer/document modifications
For the terrestrial ecosystem, the project proposes 2 trial sites: Valka-Valga intersections and Bikernieki Race Track. It is not clear in the document which use cases will be tested in each site.	Bikernieki removed. No trials there finally. This information is included in the test cases table, also included in this new document release.
For the maritime ecosystem, in both scenarios, it seems that there are two alternative paths between the vessels and the shore: 5GNSA and satellite. How is traffic split into these two paths?	Content specified in D1.13, specific Deliverable for Maritime solution.
Table 16, does it correspond to a scenario or to a test case? According to the description at the beginning of the document it seems more a test case than a scenario. Where are test cases defined?	The test cases are first resumed in a trials table and then described in detail in a dedicated table. The resume tables are presented in section 6 and all the

	test cases tables and relates scenarios in ANNEX I and ANNEX II
The document is not well written, there are many grammatical errors that make it difficult to read.	The full document has been Refined and improved.
For the scenarios listed in table format (ID, modality, location, class type) (for example, page 41) it is not clear what will be tested in each scenario, which procedure will be followed, etc. Only one test description is provided as an example (table 17). <u>Where/when are the rest provided?</u>	The test cases are first resumed in a trials table and then described in detail in a dedicated table. The resume tables are presented in section 6 and all the test cases tables and relates scenarios in ANNEX I and ANNEX II

3 Methodology, Processes, Dependencies

This section briefly resumes the methodologies adopted for the validation of 5G features during a mobile network operator transition. These methodologies have been already introduced in several deliverables [6,7,9] along the project execution.

Expanding on the common methodology identified across the 5G ROUTES project:

1. Iterative Testing and Evaluation Cycle:
 - Plan-Do-Check-Act Approach: This methodology embraces continuous improvement, starting with planning, implementation (Do), monitoring (Check), and taking actions (Act) based on results.
 - Progressive Stages: Each phase builds upon the previous, starting with controlled lab trials to test basic functionalities, moving to more complex field trials to evaluate real-world performance, and finally to analysis and refinement.
2. Use Case and Scenario Development:
 - Diverse Use Cases: The documents emphasize developing use cases that cover a broad range of scenarios in Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM), including both terrestrial and maritime applications.
 - Scenario Specifics: Detailed descriptions of scenarios ensure that the trials and evaluations are relevant and cover potential real-world applications and challenges.
3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Identification and Assessment:
 - Targeted KPIs: Selection of KPIs is tailored to each use case, ensuring a focused approach to measuring success and areas for improvement.
 - Data-Driven Approach: Emphasis on collecting and analysing data to objectively assess performance against these KPIs.
 - Technical and Business Metrics: KPIs encompass both technical aspects (like network performance) and business aspects (like commercial viability).
4. Integration and Field Readiness Testing:
 - Lab to Field Transition: Methodology for transitioning from lab trials to field trials, ensuring that use cases are robust and ready for real-world testing.
 - Integration Checks: Ensuring that each use case is properly integrated with the necessary platforms and technologies before field deployment.
5. Cross-border and Cross-domain Trials:
 - Varied Testing Environments: Trials are not limited to a single type of environment but include cross-border areas to test network performance in diverse settings.
 - Challenges of Different Domains: Understanding and addressing the unique challenges presented by terrestrial and maritime environments.
6. Feedback and Continuous Improvement:
 - Iterative Refinement: Feedback from each testing phase is used to refine and improve the use cases and the overall system.
 - Stakeholder Involvement: Collaboration with various stakeholders to ensure the trials are comprehensive and meet the needs of all parties involved.

7. Scalability and Sustainability:

- Future-proofing: Considering the scalability of solutions for future, larger-scale deployments.
- Sustainability Focus: Ensuring that the solutions developed are sustainable in the long term, both technologically and commercially.

This comprehensive methodology highlights the project's commitment to rigorous testing, continuous improvement, and real-world applicability, ensuring that the solutions developed are robust, effective, and ready for future challenges in 5G connectivity and CAM.

This aligns with the objectives outlined in section 1.1 of the 5G-ROUTES DOA [1], which involve developing and evaluating methodologies for testing and validating results. It also pertains to the technological validation of the use cases using an agile-based iterative process approach (Plan-do-check).

3.1 Methodology

In 5G-ROUTES experimental Eco-system end users will be able to perform, in near real-time conditions, advanced technological validation of highly innovative and future oriented use cases. The experimental process, relying on methods that come close to agile ways of work, will carry out technological validation based on the following stages:

Phase 1:

- To begin, an overview of the general planning and description of the use cases (UCs) from a logistics point of view is presented. The initial round of 5G NSA trials, originally scheduled for Autumn 2022, was scrapped to allocate ample resources for 5G SA testing. The trials will now be focused in 2024, coinciding with the availability of the 5G network infrastructure and a Local Breakout roaming solution. These trials will consist of two brief phases:

For the Maritime ecosystem:

- The preliminary deployment will concentrate on evaluating the technical feasibility of multi-hop.
- The second deployment will assess selected use cases.

For the Terrestrial ecosystem:

- The preliminary deployment will involve basic scenarios and focus on assessing service disruption and validating interaction with the CAM Services Platform.
- The second deployment will encompass large-scale field trials.

Section 5 reports in detail, with a focus on the locations, facilities, infrastructure and timeline for every considered Eco-system. Section 6 presents an initial introduction to the use cases, along with their classification into eco-systems. Subsequently, some templates are introduced for defining and describing the UC experimental scenarios. These templates will be completed by all project partners and can be found in Annex 1: Use Cases Trials Descriptions per Eco-system.

Phase 2:

- Afterward, the setup plan of test procedures and the related reporting tasks are defined for the individual UCs. To facilitate this stage, we provide a template for each UC, accompanied by an exemplar of a fully filled-out template. Within this template, each partner will furnish the specifics concerning scenario identification and its fundamental conditions in the next phase.

Phase 3:

- The third and main step is related with the execution of the test procedures for the UCs, measuring the KPIs and validating the results from a technological point of view. This activity will be carried out in T4.2 and its results collected in the related deliverable.

Figure 1: Simplified flowchart illustrating the technological validation process.

In our proposal, we refer to several methodologies to signal our preferred way of work: agile approach and methodology, iterative development process, agile-based process, service design, design thinking, co-creation and lean start-up methodology.

As the first approach is the agile methodology, we refer to Deming’s Plan-Do-Check-Act as the fundament for use cases’ iterations. Although these approaches may vary, they all share crucial components for the 5G-ROUTES experimental phase:

- The specific use case scenarios will be tested and validated in by iterations between lab trials and field trials refining the technological implementation.
- Test as cheap as possible in early phases, in order to avoid investments which are not addressing real difficulties. The scenarios are first tested in the lab to limit their costs especially in set-up phases.
- Establish a clear understanding of the stakeholder who has some job-to-be-done or pain point to be addressed. Here, the use of “minimum viable product” method is preferable.
- Implicitly, it is understood that the problem or pain point to be addressed is stabilised at some point of time, and that the iterations are concentrating on the technical adaptation and validation provided by simplified (first phase) and extended (second phase) field trials.

Figure 2: (A) Deming’s cycle. (B) Agile ways of work.

3.2 How to Facilitate Agile Way of Working

These above-mentioned components or phases are usually illustrated with a cycle, as in Deming's cycle¹, Lean Start-up² - see illustrations in figure 2 (A and B). When design thinking is integrated as a part of methods used, the cycle will include a stage with a stabilised value problem scenario³ as shown in figure 3.

Within design thinking approaches, we also find the use of personas⁴. Personas are fictional characters which are created in order to represent the different end-users in a consumer setting or, for instance, ecosystem actors/stakeholders in a professional setting. Such imaginary personas are thought to develop or use your service, product, site, platform or brand in different ways. Creating personas enables you to better understand pain points, needs, experiences, value perceived, behaviours and goals when developing and testing new product/service or processes.

With these illustrations and sources, we suggest that technical and business validation refer to two different aspects of working agile, precisely the technical validation is to test if it is possible to solve the pain point technology wise.

3.3 Introduction to the Test Methodology

In support of 5G-ROUTES vision to enable different service providers to conduct a set of experiments of their multiple use cases in both the terrestrial and the maritime ecosystem, section 4 proposes an approach towards a unified methodology for the test reports formats and the technological validation adapted to the 5G-ROUTES approach.

Figure 3: Overall scoping of the test reports format methodology.

Figure 3 illustrates the main parts of the test reports format methodology: at its core it focuses on the formalisation process. Precisely, the formalised test case specification phase using as its “Foundations” some key concepts supported by important terminology definitions to help identify the test entities across methodologies.

In order to provide a full testing life cycle and all the necessary validation and verification (V&V) tools to the 5G-ROUTES with the support of the work from T1.4, a “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of results” module idea is explored with the definition of its initial requirements.

¹ https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newPPM_89.htm

² <http://theleanstartup.com/principles>

³ <https://www.alexandercowan.com/venture-design/>

⁴ <https://www.alexandercowan.com/tutorial-personas-problem-scenarios-user-stories/>

Its main goal for the first phase of the project and for the first version of this deliverable is to provide to all UCs partners a set of templates to enable:

- the extraction and description of the scenarios to be validated per use case in the different UCCs.
- a test analysis to provide the steps for deriving the test cases, using a formalised test specification format common to all UCs while considering their specificities within their categories.

Figure 4 illustrates the basic entities and their relationships that form the core concepts (“Foundations”) that the methodology has been built on.

Figure 4: From Use case to Test Case.

To conclude on this brief introduction, once the test executions start, the test cases will be gathered, collected, analysed into different test report formats to provide a real insight into the experiments. Then, the results will form the final report including the methods and formats involved that are not covered in this first version of the deliverable.

3.4 Introduction to the Technological Analysis and Validation Methodology

This section presents a short introduction of the technological analysis and validation methodology. This involves adjusting potential validation frameworks inspired by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) and other 5G research projects ((Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation Working Group, n.d.), (5GPPP/5GVINNI, n.d.)).

From an overall perspective, the methodology encompasses analysis of the foundations, including terminology and concepts and the definition and elaboration of methodology around a central notion: the testing regime.

As illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4, there is a close relationship between this methodology and the methodology for formalisation (test report formats, parameters, etc.). As previously stated, the notion of “testing regime” is the central concept to this methodology.

In Figure 5, an overall flow of elements and topics to consider and analyse is included. The tests and the final validation steps methods have been considered because of the processes employed in the 5G solutions project

[5]. The testing of the UCs using multiple tool sets is executed in front of the validation of E2E trial of vertical use cases to prove the 5G-ROUTES capabilities.

Figure 5: Reference on test and validation methods from 5G-SOLUTIONS employed in 5G-ROUTES.

The following topics should be assessed in the technological test and validation process:

- Array of test cases/scenarios and test types covered;
- Different test types and different testing tool types applied;
- Test architecture and systems for visualisation of data applied;
- Use of automatically execution of test cases;
- Use of acceptance testing methods.

With respect to readiness testing methods, we find the following types:

- “System readiness testing (Beta testing)”: for tests whether the user verify the solution deployed.
- “Operational testing”: for tests whether processes and procedures are in place and allows a system to be used and maintained, e.g. training, security etc.

Below, in Figure 6, ETSI presents their testing as a service system (TaaS). Different test types are presented, depending on whether they are network related or application related. For 5G-ROUTES the performance (services’ continuity during cross-border situations) is tested on both levels using different tool types.

Figure 6: Example of test types and tools from 3GPP/ETSI.

Categorization here is based on which technology and tests that are covered, e.g. performance of the NFV Infrastructure (Network Function Virtualization), testing and verifying both the network performance and the service performance using Quality of Experience (QoE) methods for a high level end-to-end (E2E) perspective.

Test cases developed for 5G-Routes follow the same methodology of the implemented for 5G-SOLUTIONS [5]. This structure starts by introducing the pre-conditions, test set-ups and requirements for pre-qualification of the tests, followed by description of the test parameters for the test cases in the test area. Moreover, the method of computing the KPIs from the actual measurements is described. Then, all the KPIs are listed for and the required value for each KPI. Finally, the post conditions are listed for all tests and the procedure and requirement of the actions that should be taken after each test case is executed.

A testing architecture should also be illustrated and described. Data flow from service level, network level and potential cloud infrastructures should be addressed, in addition to the role of test executor and other entities. A proposal for automation of the test cases could address topics such as whether test cases are translated to executables files, test steps, the position of the test executor engine, use of API's and actual drivers translating the equipment API into generic ones.

3.5 Terminology

This section presents all the terminologies before the test process is introduced. It concentrates on giving a basic definition of the important terms used throughout Sections 4, 5, 6 & 7 around three key entities: the test basis (the requirements), the test object (or the system under test) and the test case (a broad term to describe the set of test artefacts).

Starting with the test basis, the following terms are defined (for more details on the test basis, D1.2 [6] is the primary source):

- **Eco-system:** group of use cases that share a common Eco-system for the demonstrations.
- **Use case:** a refined, unique set of requirements with their detailed description, their target KPI and SLA values, requirement analysis and testbed mapping.
- **Service Class:** refers to the ITU-T- service Classes: eMBB, mMTC, URLLC.
- **KPI:** refers to the target technology key performance indicators associated with a use case.
- **Requirement:** a broad term to denote a piece of requirements as outlined in D1.2 [6] and D1.8 [7] for a particular use case.
- **Scenario (use-case scenario):** for each use case a number of scenarios might need to be validated which could be defined, identified by their respective critical/crucial tasks along with the different actors and their interactions with different systems or 5G uninterrupted coverage and services, including any additional information and will be referred here by a scenario identifier.

As for the test object, the followings are used and required to be defined:

- **SUT:** the system under test term might be used as a broad term for the piece of software, hardware or/and network that is being tested, it can also be referred as the test object.
- **Test System:** refers to existing, new test frameworks where the test cases might be stored, compiled, executed from.
- **Test Tool:** equipment (hardware, software or virtualized) used to measure the performance of SUT.
- **Reference Equipment:** a broad term referring to a software, hardware used as part of the test object.
- **Testbed:** refers to the entire platform for conducting the validation of an experiment.
- **Test Point:** is identified by its location on the end-to-end test platform where measurements are collected, the definition of the KPIs will drive its definition. A set of test points will be defined per experiment where their locations could be either the user equipment, or somewhere on the network or on the application server for example.

And finally, the terms around the actual test process, activities and artefacts which are developed in detail further in this document:

- **Test Process:** refers to all the phases and relevant activities identified to produce the desired outcome for this deliverable.

- **Test Analysis and Design:** a phase where the requirements are analysed and mapped to a set of test cases.
- **Test Specification:** a phase where a set of templates is proposed to translate the use case-scenarios into an executable format: the test case specification.
- **Test Objective:** high level objective of the use-case scenario, additional objective might be identified and mapped to specific test cases.
- **Scenario (system scenario):** refers to a specific systems configuration, a test case might be executed under a number of system scenarios.
- **Test Case:** an entity that combines information regarding the test objectives, the use-case scenario and network scenarios to be executed.
- **Experiment:** combines all information from one or more test cases and their associated systems scenarios into one entity.
- **Test Report:** it refers primarily to the set of test cases executed by each use case. A number of reports with different formats will be proposed to provide a very detailed insight into the experiments.

A number of the project documents have been reviewed in order to define the proposed formats, templates in section 4 & 5. These templates are the results of combining the findings from those documents but also using a number of existing standards (ETSI Centre for Testing & Interoperability, n.d.).

It is envisaged that the proposed templates will be continuously reviewed and improved through different versions as the task T4.1 progresses towards the final report (D4.9).

The identifiers are created as per the following convention:

- Scenarios: ENVz_UCx.x_F/LTx_SCxx (z = Environment ID, x.x = Use case ID, x= Field/Lab Trial index, xx = Scenario ID)
- Test Objectives: ENVz_UCx.x_F/LTx_SCxx_TOn

Where ENVz_UCx.x_F/LTx_SCxx is the use case-scenario id, and xx corresponds to a sequential number starting from 1.

4 Test Reports Format, Formalization and the Test Regimes

4.1 Approach

Figure 7 below is an illustration of the iterative approach adopted for T4.2 (Technological Validation). With its four main phases at the centre, its relationships with the other 5G projects, 5G-ROUTES work packages and tasks: It allows for incremental and continuous improvements of the methodology itself (both at the overall level as well as at the level of individual use cases) but also of the trials executions using a feedback loop to get real insight and the best results.

The four main phases are further elaborated below in Sections 6, 7 & 8 where the overall testing and validation process is elaborated.

Figure 7: High Level Approach.

4.2 Background Inputs

1. **Previous 5G-PPP projects:** The very first activity for taking on the work was to spend valuable time reviewing, analysing and learning from the various existing documents from other projects. Despite their various approaches and various in-depth levels. It was a real opportunity to get an insight into the different test methodologies defined but also a “how-to” guide for the test specification activity along with the creation of the different required templates. The list below provides a summary of some of the deliverables reviewed so far from previous 5G-PPP projects:
 - **5G-SOLUTIONS:** Formulating a wide set of innovative, heterogeneous use cases spanning across five vertical industries and providing the technological enablers for the execution of the field trials. The similarity of this project contributed a valuable starting point for UCs and Scenarios description and validation methodology.
 - **5G-TOURS:** The 5G Tours testing framework consists of several components, including the 5G Tours simulator, which simulates 5G networks and allows for the testing of various network scenarios and the 5G Tours dashboard, which provides real-time information about network performance. The 5G Tours testing framework is designed to be flexible and customizable, allowing users to tailor the testing scenarios to their specific needs.
 - **5G-EVE:** 5G-EVE facilities: Use of the 5G-EVE Turin facility for conducting field trials for the use cases related to the smart energy living lab. 5G-EVE deliverables give an overall view of a structured test approach: from test plan to test procedures along with some validation tools and also include a KPI collection framework.

- **5G-MOBIX:** The framework is designed to evaluate the functionality, interoperability, and performance of 5G network equipment. The test cases are designed to simulate real-world scenarios, such as handovers between base stations and network congestion, to ensure that 5G networks can deliver high-quality and continuous services to users.
 - **5G-TANGO:** An immersive E2E streaming service, able to fuse video streaming as 360° in AR/VR personalised content; VNFs: content management, aggregator, reverse proxy, streaming servers. The 5G-TANGO project and its deliverables provide a really good insight on how an advanced V&V platform can be used for their selected use cases. Their test framework uses Model-based testing to automatically generate the tests and also includes a certification platform.
 - **5G-VINNI:** 5G-VINNI facilities: Use of the 5G-VINNI facilities for conducting field trials for the use cases related to the factories of the future (Ireland, Brussels, Norway), smart cities (Ireland), smart ports (Norway) and media & entertainment living labs (Patra and Norway). Another interesting, structured test approach with great focus on the formalisation process with very detailed templates and initial test reports.
 - **TRIANGLE:** Framework for 5G applications and devices testing and benchmarking. The deliverables reviewed give a complete and final test specification report with a format that uses a modular approach to the test case formalisation.
 - **5G-GENESIS:** A large-scale facility and an open set of tools for 5G Experimentation. An in-depth approach is taken on the concept of experimentation with associated procedures and templates which also provide early results from the first cycle of trials.
2. **Previous 5G-ROUTES WP1 (Requirements' analysis, use cases and preparations for CAM tasks) tasks:**
An important source of information for this D4.1 has been the deliverable D1.2 (Use cases scenarios specs target KPIs for 5G for CAM). With its analysis of the use cases including an initial version of the KPIs to be measured: it documents, covers the needs and the requirements from an E2E perspective which feeds into other critical tasks and certainly sets out a foundation for our tasks.

As for D1.8 (Test Framework) has contributed to influencing the testing process as a whole for T1.4, also leading to the development of a better understanding of the challenges ahead of providing E2E services in the 5G-ROUTES ecosystem.

3. **ETSI Approach to Testing** (ETSI Centre for Testing & Interoperability) With its focus on Conformance, Interoperability, Testing and Standardization in a multi-vendor, multi-network, multi-service Eco-system, ETSI documents are a good reference for many of the objectives set out in this deliverable: starting from test methodologies, test processes and procedures, test specifications to test case formalisation process and test reports but also the key concepts around test eco-systems to enable the control over the test execution and collection of measurements (see Figure 8 below). Like any other standards, the work conducted by the different bodies involved can be freely used and will therefore further feed into D4.1 where appropriate.

Figure 8: ETSI Illustration of an NS under Test.

4.3 Feedback Loop

This section outlines the importance of getting feedback from other WP4 tasks and WP1, WP2 and WP3, including the trials, by providing an opportunity for partners to give possible solutions, processes and tools for an efficient feedback loop which will guarantee the compliance with the set of objectives for both tasks and beyond. This area will be further developed in the second phase of the project.

1. Next 5G-ROUTES WP4 tasks:

T4.1 is closely related to T4.2 namely “Large-scale cross-border field trials execution” and T4.3 “Performance evaluation and lessons learned”, for the technological validation and leverage of 5G capabilities. BRA, together with EEE and IQU will work together, having frequent meetings and acting as peer reviewers with the aim to improve 5G facilities and infrastructure throughout every agile-based iteration for each use case.

2. Other 5G-ROUTES WPs: WP1, WP2 and WP3

The 5G-ROUTES experimental and validation activities were planned into three different testing cycles or iterations. After each cycle, the findings collected will influence the experimental methodology, i.e. defining new tests to run to ensure correct and expected functionalities are in place. The iterative approach will also be used to incorporate more features as the project progresses. Taking as an example the infrastructure, the first simplified phase will experiment with the services in a fresh deployed SA Eco-system while the infrastructure in the pilot locations will be adjusted to the final SA configuration. The related features to test are expected to be upgraded along the experimental phases, considering the experiments’ results of the previous phase or executed scenarios. The experimental phase, with the objective to test the cross-border situation, the platform will have incorporated the expected functionality as it has been initially designed. It is therefore important to ensure feedback reaches the correct recipients and that we can keep track of the flow until the feedback / issue is somehow resolved, especially amongst partners within WP1 Requirements analysis, use cases & preparation for CAM trials, WP2 Development of technological enablers for CAM trials and WP3 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness.

A first step here is to employ mailing list where all partners involved in the feedback loop will be included. Thus, there will be two points of communication for feedback regarding the document and data generated:

- Documents will be shared through MS Teams Inlecom Systems repository (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Inlecom Systems Teams repository for 5G-ROUTES Project.

- All data generated and integrated in the different tables (See **Error! Reference source not found.**) defined for each use case during the trials execution, will be transferred to the Tenant Web portal to improve the experiment's result track-ability.
 - Any information that requires to be uploaded to the portal once (i.e. UC and scenario information - see Figure 10 below) to be done by the respected partners via the TWPIUI.
 - Any information related to the experiments (i.e. id/link to the scenario, date, experiment results, etc.) to be done manually at the end of the experiment through the TWP interface. The procedures are reported in section 4 of D1.8 [7].

Figure 10: Tenant web portal for 5G-ROUTES Project.

The phase in which each UC will be tested are aimed to demonstrate how current 5G capabilities can be leveraged for different applications and their connected services in each use case and provide requirements and suggestions to further improve both functional and non-functional capabilities of 5GROUTES infrastructure.

4.3.1 Test Reports and Results

Is mandatory, to track the results and the related tested scenarios, to employ the Scenario identifier (see Section 6.1) to save all the related data. The Scenario repetitions will be identified adding an R and an index at the end of the Scenario ID under test (i.e. TER_UC1.1_FT1_SC1_R1).

Once the test execution finishes, the use case owners are responsible of data collection from the devices and systems involved. As already introduced in the previous section and reported in detail in D1.8 [7] section 4, the

available procedures related to the experiments results collection are due to the use case trials responsible, commonly the Use Case owners. The responsible will collect the data logged by the several systems involved and upload this data to the TWP data base, employing the TWP user interface. Once the data is uploaded to the TWP. It's visualization and presentation will be matter of the same TWP, and the different available representation methodologies, as reported in D2.7 [8]. After the uploading step all the data reported to the TWP will be immediately available for its visualization.

4.4 Testing regime

After the test analysis, the testing regime outlines how tests are set up and executed to validate the technology KPIs for each use case. It also allows for conclusions to be drawn regarding the performance of the tested use cases and specific scenarios. It can be discussed from several perspectives, for example testing framework, test types and test tools.

4.4.1 Testing framework

The testing framework specifies the test platform and test execution process.

The test platform consists of a set of tools that allow to carry out the experiments. The basic components for 5G-ROUTES experimental platform are the following:

- **Test portal** is the interface for test management. It allows 5G-ROUTES use cases to define, create and execute tests.
- **Test tools** are the testing and monitoring tools used to supervise the 5G network and infrastructure.
- **SUT** defines the system under test, which could be network elements, the 5G network (E2E) provided by the 5G-ROUTES project infrastructure implementation, or the 5G uninterrupted coverage and services that the 5G-ROUTES use case provides.

The test execution process includes the following steps:

- **Pilot site readiness:** all infrastructure and services, which the use cases need for the experiment are set up and ready to be used.
- **Test case preparation and configuration:** the needed equipment is brought on site, and tests are performed that everything works and briefing of all actors involved.
- **Experiment execution:** repetition of the experiments under similar circumstances
- **Data upload:** verification of the results and upload of the test results to the Tenant Web
- **Data analysis:** calculation of the KPIs for the experiments and aggregated values for the test case.

The testing framework will be further detailed and extended to be aligned with the ongoing work on the 5G-ROUTES KPI Visualization system. The documentation of the extended framework will be provided in later living document versions (project internal) and in the final version of this deliverable.

4.4.2 Test types and test levels

The focus of this deliverable is on defining the test cases at an end-to-end test level and primarily from a performance test type point of view. However, a bottom-up approach is taken to identify new test types and test levels while information is gathered for the test specifications.

Therefore, the next deliverable is likely to include reports on test cases conducted at lower test levels but also will include test types other than just performance (see classification below). So far, the test types identified are classified into:

- **Readiness test:** verify that the service provisioned to the use case is correctly deployed and activated.
- **Performance test:** verify the performance of the provisioned system when the connectivity is interrupted due to an operator change. Once the clients connect to the service instantiated in the visiting domain, the systems performance, about how the cross border operations affected to the client at

application level, will be assessed. The performance is measured as KPIs. Depending on the type of SUT, performance test can be further divided into:

- Network Element performance test: verify the performance of a network element that could be a specific network component or a network domain (such as RAN, Transport network, core network or edge cloud). If a use case has its own VNFs (e.g., application VNFs) or network domain (e.g., 5G NR node) integrated with the 5G network platform, then this test is of interest to the use case to improve and/or optimise the performance of the specific VNFs or network domain.
- E2E application performance test: verify the performance of the 5G uninterrupted services that the use case provides to the end users or end devices. Note that the end point of this E2E test indicates the end user/device and the performance measurement could be application-specific KPIs (refer to D1.2). This type of test will be designed and developed by the use case owner.

5 Phase 1 – Field Trials Planning

The following sections will provide information about the implemented infrastructure, trials sites, facilities and timeline related to each of the field trials eco-systems prepared.

5.1 Terrestrial Eco-system

The terrestrial Eco-system will support the majority of the use cases developed in the project. For the terrestrial Eco-system the use cases have been grouped as following (More details in Section 6):

- See-Through Platooning
- Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving
- Infotainment

The grouping by eco-systems has the intention of combine the use case involved and optimize the logistics and organization of the trials and demonstrations. As example the infotainment use cases will exploit the transport provided by the CAM Use cases. The concurrent realization of experiments of different systems at the same time could be of benefit for the results interpretation and to get more insights about how similar system works in similar conditions and if there are differences in the results obtained that can lead to improve or optimize some of the tested systems.

5.1.1 Infrastructure configuration

As the Teleoperators involved in the project dropped out, the infrastructure and related solutions has been redesigned to employ just one Core, property of the partner TTU.

The infrastructure Core is placed in the university campus, in Tallin. The position of this place with respect the field trials locations is depicted below in Figure 11.

Figure 11: 5G Core location and trials sites.

The Core setup that will support the project infrastructure, as shown, is installed at TTU premises. This Core will support the trial sites selected, for the Terrestrial Eco System, trough cabled connection, thanks to the support of the operators previously involved in the project, LMT and Telia, and the partner EEE. The detailed description of the deployed infrastructure will be presented in the deliverable 3.10 “Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness, final version”.

5.1.2 Location

The experiments related with the terrestrial Eco-system will take place at two experimental sites previously prepared in terms of infrastructure thanks to the work carried out in work package 3: The municipalities of Valka and Valga.

5.1.2.1 Valka-Valga Municipalities

These municipalities have been involved from the initial steps of the project. Their involvement consisted, during the first contact, on the selection of the roads intersections that have been employed (Figure 12) to install the equipment necessary to the second use case of the Terrestrial Eco-system (Table 6).

Figure 12: Valka-Valga instrumented intersections.

The Valka intersection that has been instrumented is positioned at the crossing of A3(P22) road with Ausekļa iela street (GPS cords: 57.785577, 26.013605; <https://maps.app.goo.gl/dhGjR2VuKRGhsWwe8>).

The smart intersection of Valga is positioned at the crossing of Viljandi tänav road and the A3(P22) Road (GPS cords: 57.790306, 26.033227; <https://maps.app.goo.gl/eAL6tPnvo7Jpig3W9>).

As reported in D3.1 “Infrastructure setup for CAM” section 4 these locations have been prepared by the previously involved Teleoperators for the network side. The smart crossing involved have been instrumented by the partners involved in the UCs that employ these facilities. A sample of what has been deployed in these intersections is shown below in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Equipment deployed at Valga intersection.

As the infrastructure provided (just one core) will not allow to test a cores migration solution, the service migration will be possible just from Latvia side to Estonian side exploiting the inter-PLMN solution developed by EEE. This condition pushed to focus on the network setup on the Latvia side to ensure that the coverage of the areas where the cars will travel to cross the border is properly trimmed with the physical border location (Figure 14).

Figure 14: base stations positions and coverage at Latvia side.

5.1.3 Facilities

5.1.3.1 Valka-Valga Intersections

For the use case II, intelligent traffic lights have been installed at intersections of the E264: at the intersection Rujienas street – Viljandi street – Transpordi street in Estonia, and at the intersection of Rujienas-Ausekla street on the Latvian side. The test site is described in more detail in D3.1, section 4.2 [8].

The facilities required by the trials are parking to set up the car as far as covered space to host the field trials staff. A relevant solution for this purpose has been identified near the Valka-Valga intersections where several parking are available (see Figure 12).

The following facilities and contacts should be considered for the trials planning and preparation:

- a room/location for the project team (management of the tests, verification of the test results....) with parking space for the vehicles near the test route.
- safe storage/parking location for the vehicles between the tests and overnight.
- information to plan the test route: coverage of the stations (and information whether there are locations along the public road where the experiments can be started, i.e. where the vehicles can be parked for a brief time).
- contact information to technical people for issues related to the network during the test period (and their availability).

During the last interchanges with municipalities' authorities, a relevant detail about trials organization came up. As the selected path (P22, E264, A3) is part of an international route, road closure will not be possible as referred by the local authorities. The only way to execute automated driving trials in these locations is with the support of roads authorities that will escort the cars that are carrying out the trials. This detail is also relevant from a Budget point of view as the involvement of authorities (of the two countries involved) will increase the costs of the trials. For these reasons and because the project focus is not directly connected to automated driving performance but in CCAM service reliability during cross-border situation, the trials in Valka-Valga will not realize automated driving operations. All the trials executed will be with pilots and avoiding autonomous driving for roads safety reasons.

5.1.4 Timeline

Given the most updated planning details and the best understanding of the project execution, at the submission of this deliverable, the timeline below (Table 4) is expected.

Table 4: Terrestrial Eco-system timeline.

Phase	Dates
Terrestrial field trials - use case scenarios	Oct 2024 – Dec 2024

5.2 Maritime Eco-system

The 5G-ROUTES maritime ecosystem includes terrestrial 3.5 GHz, and satellite communication for backhaul connectivity and ferry coverage. These scenarios will be extended with the multi-hop connections from the shore and between the vessels.

5.2.1 Infrastructure Implementation

In the trials, two vessels of West Coast Sea Service are involved: the larger Bon Marin vessel and the smaller Marina vessel. . For the first tests, the research vessel eMV Salama from Turku University of Applied Sciences is used. The vessels are equipped with a 5G SA private radio network with a small cell 5G base station, provided by

Digita Ltd with a core from CumuCore. The small cell 5G base station is working as a moving base station. The different backhauling methods (satellite connectivity, cellular backhaul and multi-hop concepts) with the 5G Core Network of the 5G-ROUTES project are tested. The onshore public 5G NSA networks used in the tests are Telia's and DNA's 3.5 GHz network (n78).

Two different configurations were initially tested in the project:

- A. Vessel #1 (Bon Marin) is between vessel #2 and the shore and forwards the traffic from vessel #2 (Figure 15). Vessel #1 has also satellite connectivity and 5G NSA connection to shore. Vessel #2 connects to vessel #1 over private network, which relays the data through the 5G NSA or satellite.
- B. Vessel #2 (Marina) is between vessel #1 and shore and relays the traffic from vessel #1 (Figure 16). Vessel #2 has also a 5G NSA connection to shore and vessel #1 a satellite connection.

Figure 15: 5G-ROUTES maritime solution configuration A: Vessel #1 sending via Vessel #2

Figure 16: 5G-ROUTES maritime solution configuration B: Vessel #1 relays messages from Vessel #2

During the trials the tests are concentrated on configuration A.

5.2.2 Locations

The infrastructure is first tested with the equipment installed on vans in Espoo, Finland. Once the equipment is set up and working properly the experimental multi-hop infrastructure will be tested in the maritime Eco-system with the support of Cumucore, Digita and VTT.

The trial takes place along the Turku-Stockholm fairway in Ruissalo, Turku. More details about the vessels and the trial site are provided in D1.13 [14].

5.2.3 Facilities and logistics

The tests are performed in two phases:

- - tests with a single vessel. The VTT van, equipped with satellite receiver, is used as well as the eMV Salama from Turku University of Applied Science.
- test with 2 vessels from West Coast Sea service.

The tests needed to set up the multi hop solution require the following facilities and logistics:

- For Vessel #1: private 5G SA network, with n77 antenna; multi-channel router (Goodmill) and Kymeta satellite receiver for OneWeb constellation.
- For Vessel #2: private 5G SA network with n77 antenna, ZTE router.
- Availability of vessels to perform multi-hop measurements.
- Availability to send data over public 5G NSA network (n78) from Telia or DNA.

5.2.4 Timeline

Table 5 presents the timetable of the maritime tests and trials.

Table 5: Maritime Eco-system timeline.

Phase	Dates
Prototype based in vans	Spring – Summer 2024
Maritime tests with 1 vessel	August-September 2024
Final Maritime Field trials	September - October 2024

6 Phase 1 – Use Case Description

This chapter aims to describe in detail the different Use Cases deployments based on the physical environment where they will be validated and consequently demonstrated. Because the project refocused during its execution, the final selected use cases are listed below in Table 6.

Table 6: Eco-systems as UCs groups.

UC #	Eco-System Title	Class Type
Terrestrial		
<u>Use Case I: See-Trough platooning</u>		
UC1.1	Platooning	URLCC(M)
UC1.2	Cooperative lane change	URLCC(M)
UC1.3	Low-latency video transmission	URLCC(S), eMBB(M)
<u>Use Case II: Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving</u>		
UC2.1	Infrastructure Assisted Advanced Driving	URLCC(M)
UC3.1	Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness	URLCC(M)
UC3.3	Collision Warning with Mobile Roadwork Operation	URLCC(M)
<u>Infotainment</u>		
UC4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go	URLCC(M)
UC4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	eMBB(M)
Maritime		
UC1.3	Low-latency video transmission	URLCC(S), eMBB(M)
UC4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go	URLCC(M)
UC4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	eMBB(M)
UC5.1	Connected Logistics	URLCC(M)
UC5.2	Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border	MBB(S)

The Use Cases tested in the terrestrial eco system have been grouped under a more specific Use Cases subgroups with the aim of establishing some results relationships or shared analysis.

For the maritime Use Cases no subgroups have been established but the selected use cases have the objective to validate the 5G multi-hop solution gathering results to understand how the different targets (Passengers, ship security and logistics monitoring) of the use cases could be impacted by the proposed solution.

UCs Experiments Description

For every UC, a projection on the experiments to set up the systems and carry out the validation along the single experimental phase is needed. First, the definition and extraction of the different scenarios with their associated information is required.

In order to start collecting the experimental conditions and settings for every UC and its scenarios a summary table template is proposed (Table 7). This summary requires to list all the scenarios involved during the experimental phase, specifying their location, their network specification type. All the experiments and configurations are going to be tested employing a 5G Stand-alone deployment.

Table 7: Use Case Experiments Description Template.

Eco-system ID:															
UC ID:															
Title:															
UC Owner:															
UC Scenarios Description															
UC Scenario List:															
<p><i>Please provide a summary description of the experimental methodology followed to validate the scenario. A UC needs more than one scenario in order to be validated.</i></p> <p><i>A scenario is more detailed and explicit in terms of tasks to be performed between actors and systems with focus on end-to-end flow along with relevant sequence of actions, systems conditions, etc.</i></p>															
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th><i>ID</i></th> <th><i>Testing Eco-system</i></th> <th><i>Location</i></th> <th><i>Class type</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i></td> <td><i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i></td> <td><i><Location></i></td> <td><i><network spec tested></i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i></td> <td><i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i></td> <td><i><Location></i></td> <td><i><network spec tested></i></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Eco-system</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i>	<i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i>	<i><Location></i>	<i><network spec tested></i>	<i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i>	<i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i>	<i><Location></i>	<i><network spec tested></i>
<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Eco-system</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>												
<i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i>	<i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i>	<i><Location></i>	<i><network spec tested></i>												
<i>Env_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i>	<i>Maritime/Terrestrial</i>	<i><Location></i>	<i><network spec tested></i>												
<p><i>To define a scenario ID the following method is proposed → EnvX_UCx.x_F/LTxx_SCx</i></p> <p><i>Env = TER/MAR, x.x = Use Case ID, xx = Field/Lab Trial index, x = Scenario ID</i></p> <p><i>To group the lab trials with the corresponding field trials and simplify the scenarios description the first part of the scenario ID will be the same and the letters in the 3rd part of the ID will distinguish if it is a Lab Test (LT) or a field trial (FT).</i></p>															

To give an example of the complexity of this task related with the different experimental sessions, an example of a filled table is reported below in Table 8.

Table 8: Use Case Experiments Description Example.

Eco-system ID	TER/MAR
----------------------	---------

UC ID:	4.1			
Title:	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go			
UC Owner:	Brainstorm Multimedia			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>TER: The scenarios listed below have the scope to progressively adapt the developed software solution to the 5G mobile technology and its improved network features. First the virtualized service should be deployed in a domain and tested in a lab Eco-system (CTTC) to verify that all the interactions between clients, service and enablers are working properly. The same solution will be then tested in Tallin (TTU) deploying it in one of the systems that will be employed for the field trials. These testing operations will lead to a final and fully capable system that support all the enablers and clients' interactions. After this phase, the solution will be tested in field trials: first in simplified settings where just a client will cross the border and its service re instantiated in the visiting domain. After this simplified attempt and the optimizations due to its results the system will be then tested in real settings, serving a number of clients superior to two. These clients will be moving across the border onboarded on the cars employed for terrestrial use cases, replicating a real collaborative game situation involving several users that will not cross the border at the same time. This will allow to verify how the client application and service are affected during network operator transition.</p> <p>MAR: The Maritime Eco-system infrastructure differs completely from the terrestrial. This condition obliges to completely modify the service function. In this Eco-system, the service will be onboarded on the mobile cores deployed on the ships and its function will be measure the client's interruption time when the connection drops until the following connectivity fall back solution get back the connectivity to the clients.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Eco-system</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>
	TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC
	TER_UC4.1_FT2_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC
	MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC
	MAR_UC4.1_FT2_SC2	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC

As can be appreciated, the example UC needs articulated trials to carry out the validation of the systems and dynamics involved in different network conditions and locations. These templates completed by all project partners are presented in the following section. To support the technical definition of the scenarios and with the aim to optimise their organisation and execution, many different scenarios will be tested concurrently during the experimental phase. Another template related to the description for every scenario is introduced in Phase 2: Test Procedures.

6.1 Experimental sessions Plans from Use Cases

As a starting point to validate the approach and a way to get testing and demonstrating over 5G in real-world field trials, all UCs contributors have been asked to describe and provide the details for the scenarios to be validated as per UC. The information collected in this section is meant to be the final approach which will be

updated in case of planning issues. This section contains just the introductory table. The complete Sessions and Test Cases descriptions are introduced later in the document in Annex

6.2 Terrestrial Eco-system

6.2.1 Use Case I

Table 9: Use Case I Experiments description.

Eco-system ID	TER			
UC ID:	I (1.1, 1.2, 1.3)			
Title:	See-Trough platooning			
UC Owner:	EDI and VTT			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The use-cases tests are structured in such a way that every subsequent lab or field test covers more high-level and use-case-specific aspects, starting with basic functionalities of the vehicle's SW/HW pipeline and communication, with limited driving. Such tests are expected to provide meaningful insights to all use-cases developed by EDI. This is followed by more specific tests, focusing on driving/communication performance in scenarios that are closer to the actual use-cases, until final trials are performed that execute the desired use-case while performing a full KPI analysis. The Platoon Manager CAM service is initially tested locally, then in the respective CTTC and TTU testbeds, with progressively more enabler interactions.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
	TER_UC1.1_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC1.1_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC1.2_FT1_SC1	CTTC, TTU, Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC1.2_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC2	Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC3	Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT2_SC2	Valka/Valga	EMBB, URLCC	SA
	TER_UC1.3_FT2_SC3	Valka/Valga	EMBB, URLCC	SA

The scenarios involve two cars following each other. The following cars gets the video from the vehicle in front, e.g. from the platoon leader. Based on the video, the driver can make the decision to start an automated manoeuvre. After the manoeuvre, the video transmission is stopped.

The following scenarios are planned

1. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE. The video proxy is implemented on the cloud (baseline scenario). Alternatively, use of Home Routing configuration as baseline.
2. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE. The video proxy is implemented in the CAM service platform.
3. Video transmission between two UEs in the same vehicle, crossing the border
4. Video transmission between UEs in two following vehicles, crossing the border.
5. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform, using the eMBB slice.
6. Video transmission between two vehicles in a platoon including border crossing, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform, using the eMBB slice.

6.2.2 Use Case II

Table 10: Use Case II Experiments description.

Eco-system ID:	Terrestrial
UC ID:	II (2.1, 3.1, 3.3)
Title:	Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving
UC Owner:	SWA, VTT and VEDECOM
UC Scenarios Description	
UC Scenario List:	
<p>The SWA scenarios have been designed to progressively validate the technologies at both, project and use case level. SWA expects to validate network performance and safety indicators executing lab trials as well as during the field trials realized in the cross-border between Latvia and Estonia. SWA looks to validate the CAM services deployed, using specific enablers (e.g., V2X routing using MEC) from which it has defined KPIs related to the service continuity. Simultaneously, safety through the C-ITS services deployed at intersection level.</p> <p>It is necessary to highlight the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public authorities of both countries have been cooperating with the necessary authorizations to realize the installation of the road infrastructure equipment in the chosen intersections. - The cooperation with project partners (UC3.1, UC3.3) during the field and lab trials extend the scope of the analysis in term of the exchange of the C-ITS messages <p>In the VTT test scenarios a vehicle, equipped with Eco-systemal perception sensors (LIDAR + camera), generates CPM (Cooperative Perception Message), containing metadata from the objects detected. This message is published to the V2X broker, which distribute it to vehicles and UEs in the neighbourhood. The receiving vehicle can be an automated vehicle, which performs an automated manoeuvre to prevent collisions.</p> <p>The following scenarios are planned to be tested:</p>	

1. Sensor data sharing between a moving vehicle, generating CPMs, and a OBU in the same vehicle (sharing same 5G modem), with V2X broker implemented in the cloud. Alternatively the V2X broker is in the CAM Services Platform in a Home Routing configuration. Baseline test.
2. Sensor data sharing between a moving vehicle, generating CPMs, and a OBU in the same vehicle (sharing same 5G modem), with V2X broker deployed in the CAM services network
3. Sensor data sharing between two UEs, located in the same vehicle, during border crossing.
4. Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders.
5. Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders using slicing.

The VEDECOM scenarios listed below aims at assessing the performances of the 5G network and the cross-border connectivity solutions to satisfy the requirements of the use case for ensuring safety automated mobility in the presence of persons (e.g. Roadworkers) in the transport corridor. Laboratory and test track results are used to collect baseline measurements regarding 5G performances and evaluation in controlled Eco-systems TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1, TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2. Then, trials are performed at the Valga/Valka location to evaluate the performance of the different solution considered to support the service continuity during the border crossing. The use case scenarios therefore involve trialling of the roaming configurations (home routing, local breakout) - TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC1, TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC2, TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC3- and possible network extensions using C-V2X - TER_UC3.3_FT3_SC1.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
TER_UC2.1_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC2.1_FT2_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT2_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1	Versailles	URLLC(M)	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLLC(M)	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC(M)	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLLC(M)	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT2_SC3	Valka/Valga	URLLC(M)	SA
TER_UC3.3_FT3_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC(M)	SA

6.2.3 Infotainment Use Case

Table 11: Infotainment Use Case Experiments description.

Eco-system ID	TER			
UC ID:	Infotainment (4.1, 4.2)			
Title:	Multi user gaming and immersive conferencing tools on the go			
UC Owner:	Brainstorm			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The scenarios listed below have the scope to progressively adapt the developed software solution to the 5G mobile technology and its improved network features. First the virtualized service should be deployed in a domain and tested in a lab Eco-system (CTTC) to verify that all the interactions between clients, service and enablers are working properly. The same solution will be then tested in Tallin (TTU) deploying it in one of the systems that will be employed for the field trials. These testing operations will lead to a final and fully capable system that support all the enablers and clients' interactions. After this phase, the solution will be tested in field trials: first in simplified settings where just a client will cross the border and its service re instantiated in the visiting domain. After this simplified attempt and the optimizations due to its results the system will be then tested in real settings, serving a number of clients superior to two. These clients will be moving across the border onboarded on the cars employed for terrestrial use cases, replicating a real collaborative VR situation involving several users that will cross the border at the same time. This will allow to verify how the client VR Player and service are affected during network operator transition.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
	TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	CTTC, TTU, Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC4.1_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLLC	SA
	TER_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	CTTC, TTU, Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA
	TER_UC4.2_FT2_SC1	Valka/Valga	EMBB	SA

6.3 Maritime Eco-system

6.3.1 Use Case 4.1

Table 12: UC4.1 Experiments description.

Eco-system ID	MAR			
UC ID:	4.1			
Title:	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go			
UC Owner:	Brainstorm			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The Maritime Eco-system infrastructure differs completely from the terrestrial. This condition obliges to completely modify the service management. In this Eco-system, the service will be onboarded on the mobile cores deployed on the ships. and its function will be measuring the client's interruption time when the connection drops until the following connectivity fall back solution re-establishes connectivity to the clients UEs.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
	MAR_UC4.1_LT1_SC1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
	MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
	MAR_UC4.1_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
	MAR_UC4.1_FT3_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	URLCC	NSA + SA

6.3.2 Use Case 4.2

Table 13: UC4.1 Experiments description.

Eco-system ID	MAR																						
UC ID:	4.2																						
Title:	VR conferencing tool on the go																						
UC Owner:	Brainstorm																						
UC Scenarios Description																							
UC Scenario List:																							
<p>The Maritime Eco-system infrastructure differs completely from the terrestrial. This condition obliges to completely modify the service management. In this Eco-system, the service will be on boarded on the mobile cores deployed on the ships. and its function will be measuring the client's interruption time when the connection drops until the following connectivity fall back solution re-establishes connectivity to the clients UEs.</p>																							
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th><i>ID</i></th> <th><i>Location</i></th> <th><i>Class type</i></th> <th><i>NSA/SA</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>MAR_UC4.2_LT1_SC1</td> <td>Espoo/Finland</td> <td>connectivity/QoS</td> <td>NSA + SA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1</td> <td>Turku Archipelago (Ferry)</td> <td>connectivity/QoS</td> <td>NSA + SA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1</td> <td>Turku Archipelago (Ferry)</td> <td>connectivity/QoS</td> <td>NSA + SA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MAR_UC4.2_FT3_SC1</td> <td>Turku Archipelago (Ferry)</td> <td>URLCC</td> <td>NSA + SA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>	MAR_UC4.2_LT1_SC1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA	MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA	MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA	MAR_UC4.2_FT3_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	URLCC	NSA + SA		
<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>																				
MAR_UC4.2_LT1_SC1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA																				
MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA																				
MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA																				
MAR_UC4.2_FT3_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	URLCC	NSA + SA																				

6.3.3 Use Case 5.1

Table 14: UC5.1 Experiments description.

Eco-system ID:	Maritime		
UC ID:	UC 5.1		
Title:	Connected Logistics		
UC Owner:	Vedia		
UC Scenarios Description			
UC Scenario List:			
<p>Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.</p> <p>Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, i.e., transportation needs to be monitored continuously via a remote-control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity.</p> <p>Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard devices, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.</p> <p>All testing is first started in lab environment and after successful results tests are moved to outside, first in land and finally in maritime environment. When all pre-testing is accepted outside trials will be moved to actual trial environment in the Archipelago of Turku Finland</p>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
MAR_UC5.1_LT1_SC1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_FT1_SC1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_FT3_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_FT4_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry)	URLCC	NSA + SA

6.3.4 Use Case 5.2

Table 15: UC5.2 Experiments description.

Eco-system ID:	MAR		
UC ID:	UC 5.2		
Title:	Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border		
UC Owner:	WINGS		
UC Scenarios Description			
UC Scenario List:			
<p>This use case aims to provide a continuous video communication with the ferry's staff and also with the harbour's administration to lead to a safe trip for the passengers and also for the cargo that is transported inside the ferry. Lack of communication between the ferry and its staff at a cross border can possibly lead to human fatalities and damage to ferry. It focuses on the provision of live streaming services between the captain and the ferry's staff so that a smooth trip can occur throughout the trip including cross border areas. It offers the ability to cover cross-border issues, including seamless communication of high bandwidth video streaming during the multi-hop communication between harbour to ferry and between ferry to another ferry and seamless support to the captain throughout the trip.</p> <p>Basic testing will be performed in WINGS lab Eco-system and after their completion tests will be transferred to field trials in the Gulf of Finland.</p>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
MAR_UC5.2_LT1_SC1	WINGS lab	Throughput, service delay, video QoS	
MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago (Ferry to harbour)	Throughput, service interruption time at cross border, video QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.2_FT2_SC2	Turku Archipelago (Ferry to Ferry)	Throughput, service interruption time at cross border, video QoS	NSA + SA

7 Phase 2 – Test Procedures

A Test Procedure is a structured document that serves as a detailed guide for conducting specific tests or experiments, providing a clear framework that includes test objectives, acceptance criteria, detailed steps to follow, required resources, and criteria for documenting and evaluating results.

To accomplish the test procedures of each UC, a template that refers to the description of every scenario listed in the UC description table is reported below (Table 16).

First, the details related with the scenario identification and its basic conditions are reported: Its ID with respect to the UC, its location, the network specification tested and the type of 5G infrastructure employed. Then, the possibility to refer the scenario to another previously defined. This leads to simplifying its description in case the scenario is repeating the conditions of another experiment changing some of the following described sections.

The main sections are those reporting:

- Test objectives
- KPIs measured
- Actors involved
- Experimental conditions and workflow
- Required technical enablers
- Required equipment (hardware and software)

Table 16: Scenario Description Template.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	SA deployment details:
<i>ENV_UCX.X_F/LTX_SCX</i> <i>Eco-system (TER/MAR), Use Case ID, Field/Lab Trial index, Scenario ID</i>	<i>Where?¿</i>	<i>URLCC(M), eMBB(M)</i>	<i>Stand Alone 5G configuration</i>
Testing Eco-system:		<i>Report in which experimental Eco-system this scenario is carried out.</i>	
Number of repetitions:		<i>Number of trials repetitions for the scenario</i>	
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		<i>If the described Scenario is related with a correspondent Lab test or a similar, previous described, Scenario.</i>	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
<i>Please list below the sections that are different with respect to the mentioned reference scenario and proceed to fill just the relevant sections for this Scenario.</i>			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Textual description, overall summary of the scenario</i>			
Test Objective(s):			

Already listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all the objectives might apply to a particular scenario and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	<i>Example: ENVUCX.XLTX_SCX_TO1</i>
<i>Test Objective:</i>	

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	<i><SCID_TO2></i>
<i>Test Objective:</i>	

Target KPIs & Measurements:

Some are listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all of them might apply to a particular scenario and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	
<i>Measurements:</i>	

<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	
<i>Measurements:</i>	

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Textual name of an interaction/action performed by an actor.

Primary User/Actor	
<i>Tasks</i>	

Primary User/Actor	
<i>Tasks</i>	

Other User/Actor	
<i>Tasks</i>	

Pre-Conditions:

Describe conditions that must be true when the UC scenario starts, e.g. System(s) state, setup, or some pre-steps to perform by a particular actor before the UC scenario starts.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

Describe the UC scenario working process including activities and tasks.

Post-Conditions:

Describe conditions that must be true when the scenario ends, e.g. System(s) state, or some post-steps to perform by a particular actor/stakeholder after the scenario ends.

Technical Enablers requirements:

List which enablers will be required, its location and if proceed configuration details, related notes, etc.

Primary Enabler	
Type/Location	
Notes	

Secondary Enabler	
Type/Location	
Notes	

Hardware/Software requirements:

Describe which equipment (terminals, devices) and applications, etc. are needed

Additional information:

Any other information deemed useful: e.g. Network Configurations and parameters, network slice characteristics, Network status, traffic type

To give an example of the complexity of this task related with the descriptions of the scenarios, an example of a completed table is reported below in Table 17.

Table 17: Scenario Description Example.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	CTTC	URLCC(M)	SA testbed
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Eco-system		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions:		10	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the application over a 5G network in CTTC testbed facility. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in order to simulate the cross border operations in lab Eco-system.			

Test Objective(s):

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_SC1_LT1_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate service availability and functionalities

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_SC1_LT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service related issues

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_SC1_LT1_TO3
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check simulated cross border issues with simplified scenario (1 user).

Target KPIs & Measurements:

In this prototype verification context NO KPIs will be measured. The scope is to adjust the application features and the connected service to the project's specific infrastructure to obtain a first functional system interacting properly with enablers and clients and measuring the KPIs involved in these operations.

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	CTTC
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Testbed tools and access (devices, one k8s for each domain, etc.)

Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the AR game client application on a test device.

Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the virtualized service in the CAM repository.

Pre-Conditions:

1. Linux/Win machine with Python
2. GPS track loaded and simulation script ready to run.
3. Game service deployed at the cam services repo.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

1. User/s starts the Experiment in the TWP
2. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients
3. application connects to it and the session starts properly.
4. GPS simulation starts, CAM messages sent to the V2X broker.
5. The movement of all virtual items should be continuous and fluent.

Post-Conditions:

No post conditions required.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Store service Image and deployment settings

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Allow intercommunication between all the infrastructure components, clients and services

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Start/Stop experiment. Save the experimental results.

Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Allows the intercommunication of enablers, services, clients

Secondary Enabler	Assisted service continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Provide data on the new instantiated services for the cross border operations
Secondary Enabler	Proactive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Trigger the IF when the clients(leader) are approaching the border
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Game servers. Virtualized on CTTC test lab servers, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and finally updating all connected devices accordingly. ● User smart devices. Android smartphone or tablet including a camera, will display the game status overlaid on the camera capture, depending on where the player is pointing the device, and the last game update from the game server. 5G infrastructure compatibles. 	
Additional information:	

The test cases Table for all the eco-systems and related use Cases could be queried in Annex I – Terrestrial Test Cases” and Annex II – Maritime Test Cases” of this document.

8 Phase 3 – Execution of the Test Procedures

8.1 Testing Concepts and Reporting

This section describes an overview over the testing process proposed as part of the methodology for the definition of the test reports and associated artefacts as well as the methodology for the technical validation.

The process flow focuses on the continuity of the test activities, starting from the tasks T3.4, T4.3 and goes beyond the work carried out in WP4, to show how it relates and integrates to the 5G-ROUTES Use Cases – Integrated deployment and evaluation approach [1].

Moreover, this section introduces the key concepts supported, along with the formats, naming conventions, and templates employed in Section 4 & 5. These tools are utilised for collecting and analysing the necessary information to thoroughly define the test reports. This, in turn, aids in facilitating a successful field trial execution and evaluation in each use case. Additionally, it delves deeply into core components like the testing regime, encompassing the concept of a testing framework, and the procedures for technological validation.

8.1.1 Key Concepts

Although the concepts below are based on an early investigation and a test analysis of the information available at this first period of the project, it is envisaged that they will evolve over time as more details will be gathered to address, prioritise and translate the specificities of 5G-ROUTES into a unified and homogenised solution primarily for the test reports but beyond: ultimately leading towards providing better results for the project.

Figure 17: Venn Diagram.

Deriving successfully and specifying unambiguously a set of test cases, require a clear understanding of the different entities involved and their relations with each other coming from the test basis (the requirements), the test objects (system, equipment, network under test) and the test cases (to use a broad term).

Figure 18: Entities.

Figure 18: Entities.” provide a list of the different entities to be involved in the development of the test specifications. The scope of this section is not concerned with defining the test basis or the test object entities, which are covered and worked on as part of the other work packages/tasks, but they are used as the source and target where the test entities are derived from or related to. Therefore, a test-oriented view of those entities is taken, centred around their relationship with the test entities. As for the latter, the foundation for their identification and definition are taken from the 5G white paper on “Validating 5G Technology Performance” (Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation Working Group, n.d.) as a proposal to work towards a pre-standardized set of tests.

Figure 19: An Experiment Representation.

Figure 19: An Experiment Representation. provides a proposed visual representation of the relationship between a test case, a network scenario and an experiment. At the core, we have the concept of an experiment which is a combination of test cases executed under certain network and load conditions: more precisely a set of network configurations or/and slices with some parameter values described as network scenarios.

Prior to fully specifying a test case, there are a number of intermediate steps that are executed throughout the test execution cycle to ensure the right coverage and traceability all the way back to the initial requirement hence prioritising. The different format designs and specifications required are described in detail in the next section, but the figure above (Figure 19) shows clearly how the different references to the use case (service class, KPI, use case-scenario) and to the system under test can be mapped to an experiment.

8.1.2 Overall Testing and Validation Process Life-Cycle

Figure 20: Original Testing and Validation Process.

For the first version (interim) of this deliverable, four key phases have been identified and described below for a successful outcome. Upon an initial extraction of the use case-scenarios, these phases and their relevant activities will be conducted for the two project level experimental phases namely the trials execution (Figure 20). The aim is to continuously provide a way to analyse, review, assess the experiments conducted while capturing them into a formal specification:

- a. **Test Analysis and Design phase:** with its two distinct activities, it concentrates on extracting the relevant test objectives, mapped KPIs from which the test cases can be derived, and also conducting a requirement traceability and a testability assessment.
 1. Review and Analysis of UCs and Test Objectives: aim is to analyse and extract a set of test objectives for each use case-scenario, while conducting a summarization and mapping exercise for traceability and testability.
 2. Review and Analysis of UCs and KPIs: main goal here is to map out the test objectives to a number of KPIs for each use case-scenario and deciding on the number of test cases for coverage while also conducting a summarization and mapping exercise for traceability and testability.
- b. **Test Specification phase:** it aims to translate the use case-scenarios into an executable specification format: the test case specifications, and collect all the necessary parameters, collection points details (variables and their values). In the further work, attention will be put at what can be specified at the project wide level vs. what is specified at the level of the specific use case. For the latter, it will be clarified what must and should be analysed, designed and specified per use case (testing and validation methodology) prior to entering the specific activities of the use case analysis as of the pilot activities. That is, this will support the planning and execution of T4.2 and T4.3 and will also provide feedback to T3.4.
 1. Define the Network scenario: activity needed by the nature of the project where the network settings will influence the test specifications and how the systems are set up in the available network configuration that will change during the different experimental phases.

2. SUTs capture with test points identification and definition: this task identifies and tentatively maps the required metrics collection points onto its E2E system under tests and defines the parameters associated.
 3. Parameters' identification and definition: many variables and their exact values need to be identified, defined across all UCs, this task focuses on gathering, extracting the different network configurations, application setups, equipment calibration variables and so on.
 4. Test report format and specification: the last activity but also the most important one since it is the main goal of this part of the deliverable, the aim really is to put all the information gathered from the previous activities into a concrete set of test cases using a unified test report format applicable to all the UCs for each pilot.
- c. **Test Setup & Execution**: The test setup and execution will be performed according to the guidelines provided by the test regime as defined and elaborated below in Section 4.7. The following process steps have been identified and briefly defined.
1. Select testing tools and SUT based on the test case: The selection of the SUT will follow from the test specification process and the selection of testing tools will be guided by the test regime as defined below.
 2. Deploy testing tools and SUT: The deployment of the testing tools and the SUT will be guided by the test regime. The deployment guidelines will be further elaborated in later versions of the test regime.
 3. Configure the test Eco-system based on the test case and type: The configuration of the test Eco-system will be guided by the test regime definitions. These guidelines will be further elaborated in later versions of the test regime.
 4. Execute the tests: The execution of the tests according to the test scenarios and test specifications will be guided by the test regime definitions. These guidelines will be further elaborated in later versions of the test regime.
 5. Collect test data: The collection of the test data will be guided by the test regime definitions. These guidelines will be further elaborated in later versions of the test regime.
- d. **Performance Evaluation and Lesson Learned**: The performance evaluation will be based on analysis of the test data and will include performance evaluation and validation according to the KPIs set for the test scenarios. The overall and summarised technological validation of the use case will be conducted by analysing the corresponding set of test scenarios' performance evaluation and results. Accordingly, the lessons learned will be documented along with the summarised test and validation results and provided as feedback to the next use case testing and validation phase. This stage and the more detailed process steps will be detailed in the next versions of this document (internal and final).

As previously stated, the original plan involved conducting test procedures in three distinct cycles. However, following internal deliberations, the ultimate decision has been to consolidate all of these phases into a single experimental phase. The outlined phases will remain unchanged, but they will now be executed solely within the unique experimental cycle.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable presented the first approach of the strategy for producing and assessing the methodologies for the testing and technological validation of experimentation results of 5G-ROUTES' use cases.

The sections relevant to the task 4.1 have laid out the foundation for approaching the trials in a structured approach, focusing on defining the initial test phases namely the test analysis, design and test case specification with their respective activities and the production of the different test artefacts such as the initial necessary templates.

The proposed testing process aligns with the agile methodology allowing for incremental improvements within the defined test methodology but also more importantly within the outcomes namely, the tests to be carried out and the results.

This document is the result of a long and difficulty project path. The different Eco-system suffered for several changes, especially on the several testing phases reduction as like as the testing places and network deployments changes.

The whole project team reacted in the more positive way to adapt the use cases and their related applications, services, manuals, logs, test cases, objectives and resulting testing scenarios.

The result will be the best possible in terms of results reliability and consistency with the best effort for trials execution and results collection. Finally, having a set of Use Cases that will be carried out in both Terrestrial and Maritime Eco systems, the project coordination and evaluation will be able to understand the differences between the Eco systems and related network deployments and have better insights about future projects and solutions in these types of conditions.

The next steps regarding task 4.1 will be to execute the test strategy by conducting the test analysis and deriving a set of test cases with the support of the UCs owners for each of the UCs and UCCs. As we go through the unique planned experimental phase, we will make use of the test case formalisation process for producing the different test reports and give a true insight in the 5G-ROUTES project goals.

10 References

- [1] 5GROUTES - H2020. GA
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- [5] 5G-SOLUTIONS. (n.d.). D1.4A “*Methodologies for the validation of 5G and for LL measurements*”. Retrieved from <https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/>
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- [7] 5GROUTES – H2020. D1.8 “*Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0*” from <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-routes/>
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- [9] 5GROUTES – H2020. D3.1 “*Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v1.0*” from <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-routes/>
- [10] 5GROUTES – H2020. D3.8 “*Report on results of the lab trials and of the operational readiness for field trials v1.0*” from <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-routes/>
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- [12] ETSI Centre for Testing & Interoperability. (n.d.). *Testing, Interoperability and Technical Quality*. Retrieved from <https://portal.etsi.org/Services/Centre-for-Testing-Interoperability/>
- [13] Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation Working Group. (n.d.). *Validating 5G Technology Performance Assessing 5G architecture and Application Scenarios*. Retrieved from <https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/TMV-White-Paper-V1.1-25062019.pdf>
- [14] 5GROUTES (2024). D1.13 “*Analysis and demonstration of multi-hop solutions broadening 5G connection coverage at sea between vessels and coast*”

Annex I – Terrestrial Test Cases

Use Case 1.1 Test Cases

Table 18: UC1.1 Trials.

Environment ID	TER			
UC ID:	1.1			
Title:	Dynamic vehicles platooning			
UC Owner:	EDI			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The tests of EDI use-cases are structured in such a way that every subsequent lab or field test covers more high-level and use-case-specific aspects, starting with basic functionalities of the vehicle's SW/HW pipeline and communication, with limited driving. Such tests are expected to provide meaningful insights to all use-cases developed by EDI. This is followed by more specific tests, focusing on driving/communication performance in scenarios that are closer to the actual use-cases, until final trials are performed that execute the desired use-case while performing a full KPI analysis. The Platoon Manager CAM service is initially tested locally, then in the respective CTTC and TTU testbeds, with progressively more enabler interactions.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Environment</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>
	TER_UC1.1_LT1_SC1	Terrestrial	CTTC, TTU	URLLC
	TER_UC1.1_FT1_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC

Table 19: TER_UC1.1_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC1.1_LT1_SC1	CTTC, TTU	URLCC (M)	Standalone (Rel. 15)
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			

Test the platooning service in the CTTC testbed facility. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in order to simulate the cross-border operations in lab environment.

Test Objective(s):

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_LT1_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate Platoon Manager functionalities on an IP level (CTTC and TTU).

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_LT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service-related issues (CTTC and TTU).

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_LT1_TO3
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check simulated cross-border issues on an IP level (CTTC).

Target KPIs & Measurements:

In this prototype verification context, no KPIs will be measured. The scope is to adjust the application features and the connected service to the project's specific infrastructure to obtain a first functional system interacting properly with enablers and clients and measuring the KPIs involved in these operations.

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	CTTC
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Testbed tools and access (devices, one k8s for each domain, etc.).

Primary User/Actor	EDI
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy 2 instances of a vehicle terminal on a local test PC.

Primary User/Actor	EDI
---------------------------	-----

<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the virtualized service (Platoon Manager) in the CAM repository.						
Pre-Conditions:							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Linux machine with MQTT client 5. Platoon Manager deployed at the cam services Gitlab repo. 							
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. User(s) starts the experiment in the TWP. 7. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients. 8. Application connects to it and the session starts properly. 9. User 1 publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to start virtual platoon as a leader. 10. In a separate terminal, user 2 publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to join platoon created in step 4 as a follower. 11. Verify that CAM messages can be sent by the leader and received by the follower via V2X broker topics distributed by Platoon Manager. 12. Platoon leader publishes MQTT message to disband platoon. 13. Throughout the test, the Platoon Manager logs for correct platoon status. 							
Post-Conditions:							
<i>No post conditions required.</i>							
Technical Enablers requirements:							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%;">Primary Enabler</td> <td>Cam Repository</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Primary Enabler	Cam Repository	<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC	<i>Notes</i>	
Primary Enabler	Cam Repository						
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC						
<i>Notes</i>							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%;">Secondary Enabler</td> <td>V2X Broker</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker	<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC	<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker						
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC						
<i>Notes</i>							

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Assisted Service Continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Predictive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT broker in charge of exchanging messages between the Platoon Manager and virtual vehicles, and sensor data between virtual vehicles (depending on test, hosted either at CTTC or VTT premises). • User computer for hosting vehicle terminal (CTTC and TTU). • Mikrotik routers (TTU) 	
Additional information:	
-	

Table 20: TER_UC1.1_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC1.1_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLCC (M)	Standalone (Rel. 15)
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	

Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):					
No Proceed					
Brief description of the UC Scenario:					
Test the platooning service in a realistic cross-border scenario. Validate end-to-end functionalities involving vehicle and network-level applications.					
Test Objective(s):					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Validate Platoon Manager functionalities in a realistic deployment scenario.</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate Platoon Manager functionalities in a realistic deployment scenario.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO1				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate Platoon Manager functionalities in a realistic deployment scenario.				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Identify CAM service issues resulting from handovers at the cross-border.</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Identify CAM service issues resulting from handovers at the cross-border.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.1_SC1_FT1_TO2				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Identify CAM service issues resulting from handovers at the cross-border.				
Target KPIs & Measurements:					
At this stage, all KPIs will be measured, including vehicle-related KPIs (distances between vehicles) and network-level KPIs (latency, throughput, reliability).					
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>TTU</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Tasks</i></td> <td>Provide basic 5G infrastructure.</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	TTU	<i>Tasks</i>	Provide basic 5G infrastructure.
Primary User/Actor	TTU				
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide basic 5G infrastructure.				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VTT</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Tasks</i></td> <td>Provide V2X broker access.</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	VTT	<i>Tasks</i>	Provide V2X broker access.
Primary User/Actor	VTT				
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide V2X broker access.				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>EDI</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	EDI		
Primary User/Actor	EDI				

<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy vehicles and related services in the trial area.												
Pre-Conditions:													
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Linux machine with MQTT client 2. Platoon Manager deployed at the cam services Gitlab repo. 													
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:													
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User(s) starts the experiment in the TWP. 2. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients. 3. Application connects to it and the session starts properly. 4. All vehicles start driving manually. 5. User in leading vehicle publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to start platoon as a leader. 6. In all following vehicles, users publish MQTT messages to the Platoon Manager to join the platoon. 7. Platoon crosses the border; network handover is performed. 8. Platoon leader publishes MQTT message to disband platoon. 9. Experiment is stopped via TWP. 													
Post-Conditions:													
<i>Possibility to safely stop is needed.</i>													
Technical Enablers requirements:													
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 30%;">Primary Enabler</td> <td>Cam Repository</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 30%;">Secondary Enabler</td> <td>V2X Broker</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Primary Enabler	Cam Repository	<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC	<i>Notes</i>		Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker	<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC	<i>Notes</i>	
Primary Enabler	Cam Repository												
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC												
<i>Notes</i>													
Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker												
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC												
<i>Notes</i>													

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Assisted Service Continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Predictive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-3 vehicles. Two vehicles equipped with board computer, sensors, OBU. Third vehicle only equipped with OBU for transferring CAMs. • Access to CAM service platform (for V2X broker and Platoon Manager CAM service). 	
Additional information:	
-	

Use Case 1.2 Test Cases

Table 21: UC1.2 Trials.

Environment ID	TER
UC ID:	1.2
Title:	Cooperative lane-change
UC Owner:	EDI
UC Scenarios Description	

UC Scenario List:			
<p>The tests of EDI use-cases are structured in such a way that every subsequent lab or field test covers more high-level and use-case-specific aspects, starting with basic functionalities of the vehicle's SW/HW pipeline and communication, with limited driving. Such tests are expected to provide meaningful insights to all use-cases developed by EDI. This is followed by more specific tests, focusing on driving/communication performance in scenarios that are closer to the actual use-cases, until final trials are performed that execute the desired use-case while performing a full KPI analysis. The Platoon Manager CAM service is initially tested locally, then in the respective CTTC and TTU testbeds, with progressively more enabler interactions.</p>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Environment</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>
TER_UC1.2_LT1_SC1	Terrestrial	CTTC, TTU	URLLC
TER_UC1.2_FT1_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC

Table 22: TER_UC1.2_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC1.2_LT1_SC1	CTTC, TTU	URLCC (M)	Standalone (Rel. 15)
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC1.2_LT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
UC1.2 acts as an extension of UC1.1, and thus has similar network-level requirements. The main difference is in the execution of the lane change manoeuvre and the related processes that happen on nearby vehicles, e.g. when a participant changes the lane to exit the platoon.			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the platooning service in the CTTC testbed facility. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in order to simulate the cross-border operations in lab environment.			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.2_SC1_LT1_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service-related issues related to lane-change (recognition and response to the lane change by other vehicles).

Target KPIs & Measurements:

In this prototype verification context, no KPIs will be measured. The scope is to adjust the application features and the connected service to the project's specific infrastructure to obtain a first functional system interacting properly with enablers and clients and measuring the KPIs involved in these operations.

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	CTTC
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Testbed tools and access (devices, one k8s for each domain, etc.).

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	EDI
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy 2 instances of a vehicle terminal on a local test PC.

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	EDI
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the virtualized service (Platoon Manager) in the CAM repository.

Pre-Conditions:

6. Linux machine with MQTT client
7. Platoon Manager deployed at the cam services Gitlab repo.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

14. User(s) starts the experiment in the TWP.
15. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients.
16. Application connects to it and the session starts properly.
17. User 1 publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to start virtual platoon as a leader.
18. In a separate terminal, user 2 publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to join platoon created in step 4 as a follower.
19. Verify that CAM messages can be sent by the leader and received by the follower via V2X broker topics distributed by Platoon Manager.
20. Platoon leader publishes MQTT message to disband platoon.
21. Throughout the test, the Platoon Manager logs for correct platoon status.

Post-Conditions:

No post conditions required.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Assisted Service Continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC

<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Predictive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT broker in charge of exchanging messages between the Platoon Manager and virtual vehicles, and sensor data between virtual vehicles (depending on test, hosted either at CTTC or VTT premises). • User computer for hosting vehicle terminal (CTTC and TTU). • Mikrotik routers (TTU) 	
Additional information:	
-	

Table 23: TER_UC1.2_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC1.2_FT1_SC1	Valka/Valga	URLCC (M)	Standalone (Rel. 15)
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC1.2_FT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
During the field trial, the lane change manoeuvre is executed to cooperatively exit the platoon and to overtake the leading vehicle(s). It relates to UC1.1 through the Platoon Manager CAM service, but also extends it with an additional functionality.			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the platooning service and cooperative lane-change in a realistic cross-border scenario. Validate end-to-end functionalities involving vehicle and network-level applications.			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.2_SC1_FT1_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate cooperative lane-change functionalities in a realistic deployment scenario.

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC1.2_SC1_FT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Identify CAM service issues resulting from handovers at the cross-border.

KPIs & Measurements:

At this stage, all KPIs will be measured.

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	TTU
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide basic 5G infrastructure.

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide V2X broker access.

<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	EDI
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy vehicles and related services in the trial area.

Pre-Conditions:

3. Linux machine with MQTT client
4. Platoon Manager deployed at the cam services Gitlab repo.
5. Test road with the option to perform a lane-change.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

10. User(s) starts the experiment in the TWP.
11. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients.
12. Application connects to it and the session starts properly.
13. All vehicles start driving manually.
14. User in leading vehicle publishes MQTT message to Platoon Manager to start platoon as a leader.
15. In all following vehicles, users publish MQTT messages to the Platoon Manager to join the platoon.
16. Following vehicle exits platoon and attempts to overtake.
17. Vehicles cross the border; network handover is performed.
18. Experiment is stopped via TWP.

Post-Conditions:

Possibility to safely stop is needed.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	

Secondary Enabler	Assisted Service Continuity
--------------------------	-----------------------------

<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Predictive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-3 vehicles. Two vehicles equipped with board computer, sensors, OBU. Third vehicle only equipped with OBU for transferring CAMs. • Access to CAM service platform (for V2X broker and Platoon Manager CAM service). 	
Additional information:	
-	

Use Case 1.3 Test Cases

Table 24: UC1.3 Trials.

Cluster ID:	Terrestrial
UC ID:	I See through platooning
Title:	3 See-through view for safe automated overtake
UC Owner:	VTT
UC Scenarios Description	
UC Scenario List:	
<p>The scenarios involve two cars following each other. The following cars gets the video from the vehicle in front, e.g. from the platoon leader. Based on the video, the driver can make the decision to start an automated manoeuvre. After the manoeuvre, the video transmission is stopped.</p> <p>The vehicle is equipped with accurate positioning equipment.</p> <p>The following scenarios are planned</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE. The video proxy is implemented on the cloud (baseline scenario). Alternatively use of Home Routing configuration as baseline. 2. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE. The video proxy is implemented in the CAM service platform. 3. Video transmission between two UEs in the same vehicle, crossing the border 4. Video transmission between UEs in two following vehicles, crossing the border. 	

5. Video transmission and receipt by the same UE, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform, using the eMBB slice.
6. Video transmission between two vehicles in a platoon including border crossing, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform, using the eMBB slice.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC1	Field	Valga		SA
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC2	Field	Valga		SA
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC3	Field	Valga	EMBB	SA
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC4	Field	Valga	EMBB	SA
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC5	Field	Valga	EMBB	SA
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC6	Field	Valga	EMBB	SA

Table 25: TER_UC1.3_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC1.3_LT1_SC1	Valga		SA
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Video transmission and receipt by the same UE. The video proxy is implemented on the cloud (baseline scenario)			
Alternatively use of Home Routing configuration with CAM service (address does not change when crossing the border)			
Test Objective(s):			
Already listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all the objectives might apply to a particular scenario <i>inside a determined Cluster</i> and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1LT_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate low-latency video transmission in 5G network when crossing border		
KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	end-to-end communication latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software. Two Qosium probes are utilized: one in the PC connected to the UE, and one in the server. The uplink and downlink latencies are measured separately.		

<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	service interruption time
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	application level handover success rate
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	user perceived data rate
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	reliability
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the CAM service on the cloud. VTT will use its vehicle.
Pre-Conditions:	
Devices installed in 1 vehicle, and operational CAM service (video proxy) deployed on the cloud and running. The TTU RTK-GNSS test device is attached to the OBU.	
All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
- Video is activated manually and streamed to the other device.	
- Vehicle crosses border. After border crossing connects again to the video proxy on the cloud	
Post-Conditions:	
no post conditions required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud
<i>Notes</i>	in addition, MQTT broker
Hardware/Software requirements:	
Equipment needed:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 OBUs and SIMs to connect to commercial 5G network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with camera (with Mikrotik 5G modem) 	

- OBU with display (connected to the same Mikrotik)
- TTU RTK-GNSS test device
- cloud server on which CAM service (proxy) can be installed. Alternatively the video proxy is installed in the CAM Services Platform
- tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium)

Table 26: TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:												
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC2	Valga		SA												
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		CL2UC1.3SC1													
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):															
Same as CL2UC1.3SC1, but the video proxy is deployed at the CAM service platform and not on the cloud, and use of Local Breakout.															
Brief description of the UC Scenario:															
Video transmission using CAM service platform.															
Test Objective(s):															
<p><i>Already listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all the objectives might apply to a particular scenario inside a determined Cluster and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.</i></p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL2UC1.3SC1LT_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Validate low-latency video transmission and service interruption in 5G network when crossing border, with use of the CAM service platform</td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL2UC1.3SC3FT_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Assess whether the 5G test network and the 5G-ROUTES enabler allow seamless handover and service continuity when crossing the border</td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL2UC1.3SC4FT_TO3</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Assess whether enablers allow to deploy the video proxy in time to guarantee seamless service continuity</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1LT_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate low-latency video transmission and service interruption in 5G network when crossing border, with use of the CAM service platform	<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC3FT_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess whether the 5G test network and the 5G-ROUTES enabler allow seamless handover and service continuity when crossing the border	<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC4FT_TO3	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess whether enablers allow to deploy the video proxy in time to guarantee seamless service continuity
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1LT_TO1														
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate low-latency video transmission and service interruption in 5G network when crossing border, with use of the CAM service platform														
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC3FT_TO2														
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess whether the 5G test network and the 5G-ROUTES enabler allow seamless handover and service continuity when crossing the border														
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC4FT_TO3														
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess whether enablers allow to deploy the video proxy in time to guarantee seamless service continuity														
Target KPIs & Measurements:															

same as previous. Service interruption time is now primary KPI. In addition:	
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	CAM service instantiation time
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle.
Pre-Conditions:	
<p>Devices installed in 1 vehicle and operational CAM service (video proxy) ready to be deployed in the CAM service platform.</p> <p>All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.</p>	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video is activated from the TWP - PRAE activates the Video proxy in the second domain. - - Vehicle crosses border. After border crossing, and vehicle connects to the video proxy in the second domain 	
Post-Conditions:	
no post conditions required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<p>Equipment needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 OBU and SIM to connect to commercial 5G network - tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium) 	

Table 27: TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC3 Test Case

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC3	Valga		SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		CL2UC1.3SC2	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Same as CL2UC1.3SC2, but use of 2 UEs, which are installed in the same vehicle. The first OBU and UE transmit the video, the second UE receives the video. The video proxy is deployed at the CAM service platform and not on the cloud			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Video transmission between two UEs in the same vehicle, crossing the border			
Test Objective(s):			
Same as for SC2. Focus on user-perceived end-to-end latency			
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
same as previous. Service interruption time is now primary KPI. In addition:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	end-to-end user perceived latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	In order to be able to measure end-to-end latency, the two 5G modems could be installed in the same vehicle. The video camera points to a screen where a digital stopwatch is running. The video is sent to the public server using the primary router. The video is requested from the server using the secondary router (assuming the role of the following car). The video is then displayed on another screen. A smartphone takes multiple pictures of the two PC screens. Afterwards, the E2E latency is manually calculated taking the difference of the stopwatch time displayed on the screens.		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT		

<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle.						
Pre-Conditions:							
Two Devices installed in 1 vehicle, and operational CAM service (video proxy) ready to be deployed in the CAM service platform. All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.							
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video is activated from the TWP and streamed to the other device. - PRAE activates the Video proxy in the second domain. - - Vehicle crosses border. The 2 OBUs should change network at about the same time. - After border crossing, the OBUs connect to the video proxy in the second domain 							
Post-Conditions:							
no post conditions required							
Technical Enablers requirements:							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary Enabler</i></td> <td>Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>cloud</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td>the two OBUs are expected to change the network at the same time, however this cannot be guaranteed.</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker	<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud	<i>Notes</i>	the two OBUs are expected to change the network at the same time, however this cannot be guaranteed.
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker						
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud						
<i>Notes</i>	the two OBUs are expected to change the network at the same time, however this cannot be guaranteed.						
Hardware/Software requirements:							
Equipment needed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs and SIMs to connect to commercial 5G network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with camera (with Mikrotik 5G modem) o OBU with display (with Mikrotik 5G modem) - tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium) 							

Table 28: TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC4 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC4	Valga		SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		CL2UC1.3SC3	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Same as CL2UC1.3SC3, but UEs are installed in different vehicles			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			

Video transmission between UEs in two following vehicles, crossing the border.					
Test Objective(s):					
Same as for SC3. Focus on impact of distance between vehicles for service interruption.					
Target KPIs & Measurements:					
same as previous. Service interruption time is now primary KPI. End-to-end perceived latency is not measured.					
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VTT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	VTT	Tasks	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.
Primary User/Actor	VTT				
Tasks	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.				
Pre-Conditions:					
<p>Two Devices installed in 2 vehicles, and operational CAM service (video proxy) ready to be deployed in the CAM service platform.</p> <p>All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.</p>					
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video is activated from the TWP. - PRAE activates the Video proxy in the second domain. - - Vehicle crosses border, and connect to the other domain. - After border crossing, the OBUs connect to the video proxy in the second domain 					
Post-Conditions:					
no post conditions required					
Technical Enablers requirements:					

Primary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker
Type/Location	cloud
Notes	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
Equipment needed:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs in 2 vehicles and SIMs to connect to commercial 5G network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with camera (with Mikrotik 5G modem) o OBU with display (with Mikrotik 5G modem) - tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium) 	

Table 29: TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC5 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:				
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC5	Valga	EMBB+URLCC	SA				
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		CL2UC1.3SC2					
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):							
Same as CL2UC1.3SC3, but using slicing							
Brief description of the UC Scenario:							
Video transmission and receipt on the same UE, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform. The video transmission uses the eMBB slice.							
Test Objective(s):							
Same as for SC3. Focus on impact of slicing on latency.							
Target KPIs & Measurements:							
same as previous. Service interruption time is now primary KPI. End-to-end perceived latency is not measured.							
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VTT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.</td> </tr> </table>				Primary User/Actor	VTT	Tasks	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.
Primary User/Actor	VTT						
Tasks	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.						
Pre-Conditions:							

Two Devices installed in 2 vehicles, and operational CAM service (video proxy) ready to be deployed in the CAM service platform. All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.						
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video is activated from the TWP, and slices configured, and video is streamed to the other device. - PRAE activates the Video proxy in the second domain. - - Vehicle crosses border. The 2 OBUs should change network at about the same time. - After border crossing, the OBUs connect to the video proxy in the second domain 						
Post-Conditions:						
no post conditions required						
Technical Enablers requirements:						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary Enabler</i></td> <td>Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>cloud</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker	<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud	<i>Notes</i>	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker					
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud					
<i>Notes</i>						
Hardware/Software requirements:						
<p>Equipment needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs in 1 vehicle and SIMs to connect to commercial 5G network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with camera (with Mikrotik 5G modem) and display, for UC1.3 transmission and receipt, connected to the eMBB slice o OBU for additional traffic, connected to the normal slice. This could be another UC1.3 experiment, using the video proxy at the cloud (CL2UC1.3SC1). - tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium) 						

Table 30: TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC6 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC6	Valga	EMBB+URLCC	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):	CL2UC1.3SC4		
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Same as CL2UC1.3SC4, but using slicing and in platoon			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Video transmission between two vehicles in a platoon including border crossing, with the video proxy integrated in the CAM service platform, and using the eMBB slice.			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Same as for SC5. In addition:</i>	
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate accuracy and service interruption time for the location device.
Target KPIs & Measurements:	
same as previous. Service interruption time is now primary KPI.	
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	positioning service interruption time
<i>Measurements:</i>	GNSS log
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the CAM services in the CAM service platform. VTT will use its vehicle, and vehicle from another partner or rental vehicle to install the second OBU.
Pre-Conditions:	
Two Devices installed in 2 vehicles, and operational CAM service (video proxy) ready to be deployed in the CAM service platform. All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony.	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video is activated from the TWP, and slices configured, and video is streamed to the other device. - PRAE activates the Video proxy in the second domain. - - Vehicle crosses border. The 2 OBUs should change network at about the same time. - After border crossing, the OBUs connect to the video proxy in the second domain 	
Post-Conditions:	
no post conditions required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal, PRAE, ASC, V2X broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud
<i>Notes</i>	

Hardware/Software requirements:

Equipment needed:

- 3 OBUs in 2 vehicles and SIMs to connect to commercial 5G network
 - o OBU with camera (with Mikrotik 5G modem), and TTU accurate positioning device, connected to the eMBB slice
 - o OBU with display (with Mikrotik 5G modem), connected to the eMBB slice
 - o UE with additional traffic, connected to the normal slice.
- tools for latency measurement installed in the OBUs (Qosium)

Use Case 2.1 Test Cases

Table 31: Use Case 2.1 Trials.

Cluster ID:	Cluster 3			
UC ID:	2.1			
Title:	Real time Traffic Info and Cooperative Intersection Collision Control			
UC Owner:	Swarco			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The UC2.1 scenarios have been designed to progressively validate the technologies at both, project and use case level. UC2.1 expects to validate network performance and safety indicators executing lab trials as well as during the field trials realized in the cross-border between Latvia and Estonia. UC2.1 looks to validate the CAM services deployed, using specific enablers (e.g., V2X routing using MEC) from which it has defined KPIs related to the service continuity. Simultaneously, safety through the C-ITS services deployed at intersection level.</p> <p>It is necessary to highlight the following aspects:</p> <p>Public authorities of both countries have been cooperating with the necessary authorizations to realize the installation of the road infrastructure equipment in the chosen intersections.</p> <p>The cooperation with project partners (UC3.1, UC3.3, UC2.2) during the field and lab trials extend the scope of the analysis in term of the exchange of the C-ITS messages</p>				
<i>ID</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
TER_UC2.1_LT1_SC1	1 st cycle	TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn) – Taltech	URLCC(M)	NSA
TER_UC2.1_FT1_SC1	1 st cycle	Valka/Valga cities	URLCC(M)	NSA
TER_UC2.1_LT2_SC2	2 nd cycle	TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn) – Taltech	URLCC(M)	NSA
TER_UC2.1_FT2_SC2	2 nd cycle	Valka/Valga cities	URLCC(M)	SA

Table 32: TER_UC2.1_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC2.1_LT1_SC1	Taltech	URLCC(M)	Non-Stand Alone
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):			
Differences with respect to the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Verification of Network connection and road infrastructure installations</i>			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Already listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all the objectives might apply to a particular scenario inside a determined Cluster and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.</i>			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_LT1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate initial architecture / Ensure the communication between the systems		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_LT1_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix 5G Network compatibility issues		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_LT1_TO3		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check 5G network base features (service connection, data transmission).		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Some are listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all of them might apply to a particular scenario inside a determined Cluster and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.</i>			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Reliability		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Textual name of an interaction/action performed by an actor.</i>			
Primary User/Actor	TTU/ Ericsson		

<i>Tasks</i>	Provision of a stable mobile communication network
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	Valga/Valga Municipalities
<i>Tasks</i>	Provision of the required authorizations to perform the installation/configuration activities of the road infrastructure equipment
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3
<i>Tasks</i>	Definition of the data model to exchange the C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM, DENM, etc.)
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authorizations provision from the public authorities of Valga/Valga city to install the road infrastructure equipment • Traffic equipment installations in the selected intersections • Reliable connection between <i>Taltech and the Swarco Server</i> 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification of the road traffic equipment installations • Installation of Swarco Software on a server • Deployment and configuration of the Swarco C-ITS system Architecture • Swarco C-ITS services functional verification • Connection with Taltech sever 	
Post-Conditions:	
Assure the correct installation and connections of the road equipment	
Reliable communication between the systems (Taltech/Swarco)	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
No enablers needed in this scenario	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
5G Network (Private and/or Commercial)	
Additional information:	

Table 33: TER_UC2.1_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC2.1_FT1_SC1	Valka /Valga	URLCC(M)	Non-Stand Alone
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):			
Differences with respect to the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Testing of the traffic equipment installed (e.g., data acquisition from the video monitoring system) and the potential exchange of C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM, DENM) with project partners			
Test Objective(s):			
Already listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all the objectives might apply to a particular scenario <i>inside a determined Cluster</i> and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_FT1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Scenario trials / data reception and transmission		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_FT1_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Technical verification of the C-ITS systems considering the video monitoring system		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_FT1_TO3		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluation of the smart features based on AI		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_FT1_TO4		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Smart Crossings (SafeLight) (1st Evaluation)		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC1_FT1_TO5		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Initial exchange of C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM, etc) with project partners (UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3)		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			

Some are listed at a UC level in D1.12 but not all of them might apply to a particular scenario **inside a determined Cluster** and by filling out the information required in this template, it might help to identify new ones.

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Road users' detection
<i>Measurements:</i>	Clear video reception for the detection of pedestrians and vehicles

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Artificial Intelligence (AI) recognition
<i>Measurements:</i>	Recognition of pedestrians and vehicles through the swarm analytic system

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Reliability
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Textual name of an interaction/action performed by an actor.

Primary User/Actor	TTU/ Ericsson
Tasks	Provision of a stable mobile communication network

Primary User/Actor	Valga/Valga Municipalities
Tasks	Provision of the required authorizations to perform field trials

Pre-Conditions:

- Authorizations provision from the public authorities of Valga/Valga city to the realization of the field trials
- Correct road infrastructure equipment connectivity and Swarco C-ITS services deployment
- A stable mobile communication network

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

- Technical verification on site of the C-ITS systems, and additional configurations if necessary
- C-ITS service basic features testing. Including the assessment of data reception and transmission

Post-Conditions:

Correct C-ITS systems connection and the testing of features of the road equipment installed First exchange of C-ITS messages with project partners (e.g., CPM, etc.)
Technical Enablers requirements:
No enablers needed in this scenario
Hardware/Software requirements:
5G Network (Private and/or Commercial)
Additional information:

Table 34: TER_UC2.1_LT2_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC2.1_LT2_SC2	Taltech	URLCC(M)	Non-Stand Alone
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):	UC2.1_SC1_LT1		
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
<i>In comparison to the UC2.1_SC1_LT1 which looks to verify network connections and equipment installations, the UC2.1_SC2_LT2 scenario specify the systems architectures, ensure the communication between the systems as well as exchange the C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM) with project partners in the lab environment.</i>			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
<i>This scenario is addressed to validate the architecture, ensure the communication between the systems as well as to the exchange of the C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM) with project partners in the lab environment.</i>			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2LT2_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate architecture		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2LT2_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Ensure the communication between the systems		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2LT2_TO3		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Measure network latency		

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2LT2_TO4
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Traffic Light Forecast\Traffic Light Assistant
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2LT2_TO5
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Initial exchange of C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM, etc) with project partners (UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3)
Target KPIs & Measurements:	
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Bandwidth
<i>Measurements:</i>	>5 Mbps, <= 1Mbps
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Latency (ms) (Median - 50% percentile)
<i>Measurements:</i>	< 50ms, >200ms
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Latency (ms) (95% percentile)
<i>Measurements:</i>	<100ms, >300ms
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	TTU/ Ericsson
<i>Tasks</i>	Provision of a stable mobile communication network
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of a stable mobile communication network Transmission, receipt, and processing of C-ITS messages (e.g., CPM, etc.) between project partners 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario: 	
Obtain a first functional version compatible with project's mobile network Infrastructure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post-Conditions: 	
Reliable communication between the systems	
Successful exchange of the C-ITS messages	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical Enablers requirements: 	
No enablers needed in this scenario	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
5G Network (Private and/or Commercial)	

Additional information:

Table 35: TER_UC2.1_FT2_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC2.1_FT2_SC2	Valka/Valga	URLCC(M)	Stand Alone
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		UC2.1_SC1_FT1	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
<p>The extended trial goal is to perform a complete demonstration of the UC2.1. During the extended trial, the enablers deployed in the 5G Platform are used to evaluate service continuity indicators at cross-border level, while simultaneously the safety features enabled by the UC2.1. are analysed at intersection level. Therefore, to provide consolidated UC2.1 results.</p> <p>In addition, UC2.1 expects to cooperate with project partners (UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3) during the extended trial to broad the scope of the study in terms of the exchange of C-ITS messages in a cross-border trial.</p> <p>On the contrary, the UC2.1_SC1_FT1 looks to analyze safety features at intersection level and the network connectivity.</p>			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
<p><i>Perform a complete demonstration of the UC2.1. From one side, using the enablers deployed in the 5G Platform to evaluate service continuity indicators at cross-border level, while from the other, the safety features enabled by the UC2.1.</i></p>			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2_FT2_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Smart Crossings (SafeLight)

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2_FT2_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Traffic Light Manouver Service (SPATEM)

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2_FT2_TO3
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Multi-modal Monitoring

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2_FT2_TO4
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Road and Lane Topology (RLT) service (MAPEM)

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	UC2.1_SC2_FT2_TO6
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Successful exchange of C-ITS messages with project partners (UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3)

Target KPIs & Measurements:

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Bandwidth
<i>Measurements:</i>	>5 Mbps, <= 1Mbps

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Latency (ms) (Median - 50% percentile)
<i>Measurements:</i>	< 50ms, >200ms

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Latency (ms) (95% percentile)
<i>Measurements:</i>	<100ms, >300ms

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Reliability (Packet loss ratio (%))
<i>Measurements:</i>	<1%, 5%>

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Capacity
<i>Measurements:</i>	Nb devices per cell per MHz (>1, <0.2)

Primary KPI:	CAM services safety
Measurements:	Number of potential risks suffered considering the implementation of UC3.1 and UC3.3
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM
Tasks	Vehicle and Network Infrastructure
Primary User/Actor	CERTH
Tasks	VRU Device
Primary User/Actor	EDI
Tasks	UC2.2: Traffic Jam Chauffeur
Primary User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	UC3.1: Sensor Info Sharing for Cooperative Situation Awareness
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM
Tasks	UC3.3 Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance
Pre-Conditions:	
The following elements need to be working properly:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road infrastructure equipment and Swarco systems • Project partners systems, vehicles and/or devices • Stable 5G SA network communications • 5G platform 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
From the Swarco side:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data monitoring from the road infrastructure installed • Data analysis to the creation of the C-ITS Messages • Data exchange <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ to the V2X broker ○ to project partners (UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.3) • UC2.1. C-ITS services execution • UC2.1. results 	

From the 5G platform, the correct function of the enablers
Post-Conditions:
<i>UC2.1 results</i>
Technical Enablers requirements:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - V2X broker using MEC - Object data fusion for improved situational awareness - Tenant Web Portal <p><i>The remaining enablers of the 5G Platform are used in an indirect way.</i></p>
Hardware/Software requirements:
5G Network (Private and/or Commercial)
Additional information:

Use Case 3.1 Test Cases

Table 36: Use Case 3.1 Trials.

Cluster ID:	Terrestrial
UC ID:	II
Title:	Sensor information sharing for situational awareness
UC Owner:	VTT
UC Scenarios Description	
UC Scenario List:	
<p>In the test scenarios a vehicle, equipped with environmental perception sensors (LIDAR + camera), generates CPM (Cooperative Perception Message), containing metadata from the objects detected. This message is published to the V2X broker, which distribute it to vehicles and UEs in the neighbourhood. The receiving vehicle can be an automated vehicle, which performs an automated manoeuvre to prevent collisions.</p> <p>The following scenarios are planned to be tested:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sensor data sharing between a moving vehicle, generating CPMs, and a OBU in the same vehicle (sharing same 5G modem), with V2X broker implemented in the cloud. Alternatively the V2X broker is in the CAM Services Platform in a Home Routing configuration. Baseline test. 2. Sensor data sharing between a moving vehicle, generating CPMs, and a OBU in the same vehicle (sharing same 5G modem), with V2X broker deployed in the CAM services network 	

3. Sensor data sharing between two UEs, located in the same vehicle, during border crossing.
4. Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders.
5. Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders using slicing.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1	Field	Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2	Field	Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3	Field	Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC4	Field	Valga	URLCC	SA
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC5	Field	Valga	URLCC	SA

Table 37: TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:				
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1	Valga	URLCC	SA				
Brief description of the UC Scenario:							
Sensor data sharing between a moving vehicle, generating CPMs, and a OBU in the same vehicle (sharing same 5G modem), with V2X broker implemented in the cloud. Alternatively the V2X broker is in the CAM Services Platform in a Home Routing configuration. Baseline test							
Test Objective(s):							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL3UC3.1SC1ft_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Validate that sensor info is shared with low latency between two UEs in 5G network when crossing border</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL3UC3.1SC1ft_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate that sensor info is shared with low latency between two UEs in 5G network when crossing border
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL3UC3.1SC1ft_TO1						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate that sensor info is shared with low latency between two UEs in 5G network when crossing border						
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Assess service interruption time when the CAM service is deployed on the cloud.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess service interruption time when the CAM service is deployed on the cloud.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO2						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess service interruption time when the CAM service is deployed on the cloud.						
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO3</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Assess continuity of the accurate positioning service when UE crosses border.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO3	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess continuity of the accurate positioning service when UE crosses border.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	CL2UC1.3SC1FT_TO3						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess continuity of the accurate positioning service when UE crosses border.						
Target KPIs & Measurements:							

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	end-to-end communication latency
<i>Measurements:</i>	application logging and Qosium. Three Qosium probes are utilized: one in the OBU of the detection unit, one in the V2X broker, one in the OBU receiving the CPMs. The uplink and downlink latencies are measured separately
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	service interruption time
<i>Measurements:</i>	Qosium software. For this test, Nemo for analysis of the different parts of the service interruption time.
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	application level handover success rate
<i>Measurements:</i>	Application based logging and visual observation, for both UEs and overall.
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	user perceived data rate
<i>Measurements:</i>	application logging or Qosium
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	reliability
<i>Measurements:</i>	application based logging or Qosium
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	service interruption time of the RTK service
<i>Measurements:</i>	application based logging
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the V2X broker
Pre-Conditions:	
Two OBUs available and connected to the network: OBU with detecting unit, and OBU with receiving software. The OBUs are connected to the same modem.	
All devices synchronized with each other.	
One OBU installed in the vehicle, second one stationary.	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
Sensor data (e.g. parked vehicle or vehicles on public road) transmitted by the detection unit.	
The vehicle follows the test route and crosses the border.	
Post-Conditions:	

no post conditions	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	cloud
<i>Notes</i>	in addition, MQTT broker
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	V2X message routing service
<i>Type/Location</i>	VTT server or CAM service platform
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
Equipment needed:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBU's to connect to the network and SIMs to connect to the network: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 1 OBU with detection unit o 1 OBU with receiving software, connected to the same Mikrotik - RTK positioning - Qosium installed in the OBU's 	

Table 38: TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2	Valga	URLCC	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
The V2X broker is deployed in the CAM Services platform			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Sensor data sharing between two UEs, located in the same vehicle, during border crossing.			
Test Objective(s):			
same as CL3UC3.1SC1fT1. In addition:			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Assess whether the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and service continuity when crossing the border		

Target KPIs & Measurements:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1
Pre-Conditions:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1. The V2X broker is deployed on the CAM Services Platform.
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1
Post-Conditions:
none
Technical Enablers requirements:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1
Hardware/Software requirements:
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1. V2X Broker deployed on the CAM Services Platform

Table X: Use Case3.1 Scenario CL3UC3.1SC3FT1/ CL3UC3.1SC3FT2 Description

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:				
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3	Valga	URLCC	SA				
Brief description of the UC Scenario:							
Sensor data sharing between two UEs, located in the same vehicle, during border crossing.							
Test Objective(s):							
same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2							
Target KPIs & Measurements:							
Same KPIs as in TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC2							
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VTT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>provision of OBUs and vehicles</td> </tr> </table>				Primary User/Actor	VTT	Tasks	provision of OBUs and vehicles
Primary User/Actor	VTT						
Tasks	provision of OBUs and vehicles						

Other User/Actor	other 5G-ROUTES partners										
Tasks	availability of 5G network and capabilities; 5G-ROUTES enablers										
Pre-Conditions:											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs installed in the same vehicle - CAM service platform operational. - 5G network operational in trial site - All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony. 											
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UC experiment is setup from Tenant Web. All devices connected. - Detection unit activated and transmitting data - Logging start - Vehicles move across the border 											
Post-Conditions:											
At the end of the experiment, the collected data is uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal											
Technical Enablers requirements:											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary Enabler</td> <td colspan="2">Tenant Web Portal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type/Location</td> <td colspan="2">cloud</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Notes</td> <td colspan="2">UC setup, logging starting and stopping</td> </tr> </table>			Primary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal		Type/Location	cloud		Notes	UC setup, logging starting and stopping	
Primary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal										
Type/Location	cloud										
Notes	UC setup, logging starting and stopping										
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Secondary Enabler</td> <td>V2X message routing service</td> <td>Assisted Service C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type/Location</td> <td>CAM service platform, edge</td> <td>CAM service plat</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Notes</td> <td>on the edge node of the CAM service platform</td> <td>address of the vic</td> </tr> </table>			Secondary Enabler	V2X message routing service	Assisted Service C	Type/Location	CAM service platform, edge	CAM service plat	Notes	on the edge node of the CAM service platform	address of the vic
Secondary Enabler	V2X message routing service	Assisted Service C									
Type/Location	CAM service platform, edge	CAM service plat									
Notes	on the edge node of the CAM service platform	address of the vic									
Hardware/Software requirements:											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs and SIMs to connect to the 5G networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with detection unit (e.g. with Mikrotik 5G modem) o OBU with receiving software (e.g. with Mikrotik 5G modem) - Qosium installed in the OBUs 											
Additional information:											
Network handover configuration: Home Routing											

Table 39: TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC4 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC4	Valga	URLCC	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			

The OBUs are now in different vehicles.					
Brief description of the UC Scenario:					
Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders					
Test Objective(s):					
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3					
Target KPIs & Measurements:					
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3.					
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VTT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>provision of OBUs and detection unit</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	VTT	Tasks	provision of OBUs and detection unit
Primary User/Actor	VTT				
Tasks	provision of OBUs and detection unit				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>EDI or LMT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>provision of vehicle for installation of OBU</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	EDI or LMT	Tasks	provision of vehicle for installation of OBU
Primary User/Actor	EDI or LMT				
Tasks	provision of vehicle for installation of OBU				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Other User/Actor</td> <td>other 5G-ROUTES partners</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>availability of 5G network and capabilities; 5G-ROUTES enablers</td> </tr> </table>		Other User/Actor	other 5G-ROUTES partners	Tasks	availability of 5G network and capabilities; 5G-ROUTES enablers
Other User/Actor	other 5G-ROUTES partners				
Tasks	availability of 5G network and capabilities; 5G-ROUTES enablers				
Pre-Conditions:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OBUs installed in 2 vehicles - CAM service platform operational. - 5G network operational in trial site - All devices synchronized with each other using PTP or chrony. 					
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UC experiment is setup from Tenant Web. All devices connected. - Detection unit activated and transmitting data - Logging start - Vehicles move across the border. 					
Post-Conditions:					
At the end of the experiment, the collected data is uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal					
Technical Enablers requirements:					
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3					
Hardware/Software requirements:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 OBUs and SIMs to connect to the 5G networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o OBU with detection unit (e.g. with Mikrotik 5G modem) o OBU with receiving software (e.g. with Mikrotik 5G modem) - Qosium installed in the OBUs 					

- equipment for UC2.1 and UC3.3
Additional information:

Table X: Use Case X.X Scenario CL3UC3.1SC6FT2 Description

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC5	Valga	URLCC	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3, TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC4	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3, but while using slicing. This scenario may be combined with TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC6.			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Sensor data sharing between two vehicles when crossing borders using slicing. The following scenarios are possible:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combination with TER_UC1.3_FT1_SC5: 1 slice for V2X traffic, 1 slice for video - 1 slice for UC3.1, to separate from disturbing traffic 			
Test Objective(s):			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC1. In addition, to assess the impact of slicing.			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC6_TO5		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate use of slicing for sensor info sharing		
For testing the impact, an additional scenario in which both data are transmitted over the same slice is needed as baseline.			
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3.			
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3. Setup of slices in the Tenant Web Portal at start of the experiment			
Pre-Conditions:			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3. Slices has to be supported in both domains and set up in the Tenant Web			
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:			
Same as TER_UC3.1_FT1_SC3.			
Post-Conditions:			
At the end of the experiment, the collected data is uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal			
Technical Enablers requirements:			

Table 41: TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1	Satory, Versailles	URLLC(M)	NSA
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Vehicle-Pedestrian Connectivity over 5G. Test the application correct connectivity over a real 5G Network			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Initial validation communication between vehicle & VRU using 5G network and infrastructure		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Reliability		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VEDECOM		
<i>Tasks</i>	Vehicle and Network Infrastructure		
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	CERTH		
<i>Tasks</i>	VRU Device		
Pre-Conditions:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One vehicle and One VRU device are connected to 5G network. • Both devices have localization using GNSS and send to MQTT broker • MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure. 			
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:			

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• One pedestrian equipped with a 5G device send alerts of its presence• One vehicle drives along the road across the border and approaches the pedestrian location. Vehicle also send alert of its presence.• Both pedestrian and vehicle are aware of the presence of each other by receiving alerts from 5G network
Post-Conditions:
No post conditions required.
Technical Enablers requirements:
<i>No enablers needed in this scenario</i>
Hardware/Software requirements:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• VRU Device• Vehicle OBU• 5G Network (Private and/or Commercial)
Additional information:

Table 42: TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:								
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1	Valga/Valka	URLCC(M).	NSA								
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		UC3.3_SC1									
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):											
Similar scenario tested in the pilot site											
Brief description of the UC Scenario:											
Vehicle-Pedestrian Connectivity over 5G . Test the application correct connectivity over a real 5G Network											
Test Objective(s):											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Evaluation of data messages exchange through 5G network, and technical validation of the pilot site.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluation of data messages exchange through 5G network, and technical validation of the pilot site.				
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC1_TO1										
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluation of data messages exchange through 5G network, and technical validation of the pilot site.										
Target KPIs & Measurements:											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>End-to-End Latency</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Secondary KPI:</i></td> <td>Reliability</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency	<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.	<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Reliability	<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency										
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.										
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Reliability										
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission										
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>VEDECOM</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Vehicle OBU</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>CERTH</td> </tr> </table>				Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM	Tasks	Vehicle OBU	Primary User/Actor	CERTH		
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM										
Tasks	Vehicle OBU										
Primary User/Actor	CERTH										

<i>Tasks</i>	VRU Device
Other User/Actor	LMT & TELIA
<i>Tasks</i>	5G network available
Other User/Actor	VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Access to V2X Routing enabler
Pre-Conditions:	
Similar to TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
Similar to TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1.	
Post-Conditions:	
<i>No post condition required</i>	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC
<i>Type/Location</i>	
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
Similar to TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1.	
Additional information:	

Table 43: TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2	Valga/Valka	URLCC(M).	NSA
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Infrastructure to vehicle connectivity over 5G: Test the behaviour of hazard detection application when crossing one intersection, i.e., in the presence of not connected pedestrian			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Transmission, receipt and processing of C-ITS messages (CPM) between infrastructure and vehicle		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by the infrastructure and its reception by the vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Reliability		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM		
Tasks	Vehicle OBU		
Other User/Actor	LMT & TELIA		
Tasks	5G network available		
Other User/Actor	Ericson		
Tasks	Provide 5G network core		

Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Access to V2X Routing enabler
Other User/Actor	Swarco
Tasks	Smart infrastructure
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One vehicle are connected to 5G network. • Roadside infrastructure is installed and can detect road users, i.e. vehicles and VRU • MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart sensors of equipped intersections detect non-connected VRU and alert about their presence • One vehicle drives along the road and crosses this first intersection and receives alert about the presence of pedestrians • Vehicle may approach intersection from different side of the border 	
Post-Conditions:	
<i>No post condition required</i>	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC
Type/Location	
Notes	
Primary Enabler	5G localization for VRU protection
Type/Location	
Notes	
Secondary Enabler	Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery
Type/Location	
Notes	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle OBU 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G Network • C-ITS Protocol Stack
Additional information:

Table 44: TER_UC3.3_LT2_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.3_LT2_SC1	Satory, Versailles	URLLC(M)	NSA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):	TER_UC3.3_LT1_SC1		
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
Additionally, test the behaviour of hazard detection application on vehicle and pedestrian sides.			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the road hazard detection, i.e., dangerous situation between vehicle and pedestrian, with V2P Communication in 5G.			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_LT2_SC1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Transmission, receipt and processing of C-ITS messages (CAM) between vehicle and VRU		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Localization accuracy		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Difference in the localization received using 5G network with the one estimated by vehicle on-board device.		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM		
Tasks	Vehicle and Network Infrastructure		
Primary User/Actor	CERTH		
Tasks	VRU Device		

Pre-Conditions:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• One vehicle and One VRU device are connected to 5G network.• Both devices have localization using GNSS and send to MQTT broker• MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure.
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• One pedestrian equipped with a 5G device send alerts of its presence• One vehicle drives along the road across the border and approaches the pedestrian location. Vehicle also send alert of its presence.• Both pedestrian and vehicle are aware of the presence of each other by receiving alerts from 5G network
Post-Conditions:
No post conditions required.
Technical Enablers requirements:
No enablers needed in this scenario
Hardware/Software requirements:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• VRU Device• Vehicle OBU• 5G Network (Private)• RTK Positioning• C-ITS Protocol Stack
Additional information:

Table X: Use Case 3.3 Scenario 5 Description

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC3	Valga/Valka	URLCC(M)	SA
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Road hazard detection when crossing multiple intersections. Test the behaviour of hazard detection application when crossing multiple intersections, i.e. when environment changes			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validation of the communication between vehicles and VRUs in different conditions, i.e. using roadside infrastructure and in out of intersection situations		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Use 5G localization for VRU protection enabler to improve detection and localization of pedestrians at the cross-border area		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC2_TO3		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluation of use case considering vehicle and pedestrians in different conditions, especially at cross border situations.		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.		
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Localization accuracy		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Difference in the localization received using 5G network with the one estimated by vehicle on-board device.		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Reliability		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Percentage of data packets which are lost during transmission		

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM
Tasks	Vehicle

Primary User/Actor	CERTH
Tasks	VRU Device & 5G localization for VRU protection enabler

Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Access to V2X Routing enabler

Other User/Actor	Swarco
Tasks	Smart infrastructure

Pre-Conditions:

- One vehicle and One VRU device are connected to 5G network.
- Both devices have localization using GNSS and send to MQTT broker.
- Roadside infrastructure is installed and can detect road users, i.e. vehicles and VRU
- MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

- Smart sensors of equipped intersections detect non-connected VRU and alert about their presence
- One vehicle drives along the road and crosses this first intersection and receives alert about the presence of pedestrians
- Eventually, vehicle crosses the border
- One pedestrian is located at a second intersection, sending alerts concerning its presence over 5G
- Vehicle approaches the pedestrian and receives the alert

Post-Conditions:

No post conditions required.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC
Type/Location	
Notes	

Primary Enabler	5G localization for VRU protection
Type/Location	

<i>Notes</i>	
<i>Secondary Enabler</i>	Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery
<i>Type/Location</i>	
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• VRU Device• Vehicle OBU• 5G Network• C-ITS Protocol Stack	
Additional information:	

Table X: Use Case 3.3 Scenario 6 Description

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC4	Valga	URLCC(M).	NSA/SA
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
VRU Collision Avoidance using 5G Connectivity. Test the capacity of the system to continuously monitor the environment even when network conditions can change due to users mobility and with multiple VRUs.			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC4_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluation of use case considering vehicle and pedestrians in different conditions, especially at cross border situations.		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Throughput		
<i>Measurements:</i>	User throughput is the number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps)		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Time to collision		
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time before two road user collide, or arrive at the same conflict point, taking into account the geometry of the road users.		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VEDECOM		
<i>Tasks</i>	Vehicle OBU		
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	CERTH		

<i>Tasks</i>	VRU Device
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Vehicles and VRU devices are connected to 5G network and have localization using GNSS.</i> • They exchange data using MQTT broker. • 5G Network • RTK Positioning available • MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VRUs can cross the street close to the intersection • Connected VRU (pedestrian & cyclist) are present in the cross-border area and may have unpredicted behavior, e.g., crossing the street with no prior notification. • Vehicle is always able to track the pedestrians & cyclists and detect any behavior leading to collision risk 	
Post-Conditions:	
No post condition required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC
<i>Type/Location</i>	
<i>Notes</i>	
Primary Enabler	5G localization for VRU protection
<i>Type/Location</i>	
<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery
<i>Type/Location</i>	
<i>Notes</i>	
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VRU Device • Vehicle OBU • 5G Network 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C-ITS Protocol Stack
Additional information:

Table 45: TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC5 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:				
TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC5	Valga/Valka	URLCC(M).	SA				
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):	UC3.3_SC6						
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):							
Similar tests conducted in cross-border conditions at the pilot site							
Brief description of the UC Scenario:							
Test Objective(s):							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC5_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Tests in the cross-border corridor in intersections equipped with VRU detection systems and in road sections not-equipped with such dedicated infrastructure.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC5_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Tests in the cross-border corridor in intersections equipped with VRU detection systems and in road sections not-equipped with such dedicated infrastructure.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC3.3_FT1_SC5_TO1						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Tests in the cross-border corridor in intersections equipped with VRU detection systems and in road sections not-equipped with such dedicated infrastructure.						
Target KPIs & Measurements:							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>End-to-End Latency</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency	<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	End-to-End Latency						
<i>Measurements:</i>	Time between the transmission of a message by a station, e.g. a VRU, its reception by an others station, e.g. a vehicle calculated using messages timestamp.						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>Application Service Interruption Time</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g. end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit)</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Application Service Interruption Time	<i>Measurements:</i>	Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g. end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit)
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Application Service Interruption Time						
<i>Measurements:</i>	Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g. end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit)						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Secondary KPI:</i></td> <td>Throughput</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>User throughput is the number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps)</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Throughput	<i>Measurements:</i>	User throughput is the number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps)
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Throughput						
<i>Measurements:</i>	User throughput is the number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps)						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Secondary KPI:</i></td> <td>Time to collision</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Time to collision		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Time to collision						

Measurements:	Time before two road users collide, or arrive at the same conflict point, taking into account the geometry of the road users.
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
Primary User/Actor	VEDECOM
Tasks	Vehicle OBU
Primary User/Actor	CERTH
Tasks	VRU Devices and 5G Localisation for VRU protection enablers
Other User/Actor	LMT & TELIA
Tasks	5G network available
Other User/Actor	Ericson
Tasks	Provide 5G network core
Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Access to V2X Routing enabler
Other User/Actor	Swarco
Tasks	Smart Intersection
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicles and VRU devices are connected to 5G network and have localization using GNSS. • They exchange data using MQTT broker. • Roadside infrastructure is installed and can detect road users, i.e. vehicles and VRU • 5G Network • RTK Positioning available • MQTT broker is installed in the infrastructure. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VRUs can cross the street close to the intersection 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connected VRU (pedestrian & cyclist) are present in the cross-border area and may have unpredicted behavior, e.g., crossing the street with no prior notification. • Vehicle is always able to track the pedestrians & cyclists and detect any behavior leading to collision risk 							
Post-Conditions:							
No post condition required							
Technical Enablers requirements:							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary Enabler</td> <td>V2X Routing over MEC</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC	<i>Type/Location</i>		<i>Notes</i>	
Primary Enabler	V2X Routing over MEC						
<i>Type/Location</i>							
<i>Notes</i>							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary Enabler</td> <td>5G localization for VRU protection</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Primary Enabler	5G localization for VRU protection	<i>Type/Location</i>		<i>Notes</i>	
Primary Enabler	5G localization for VRU protection						
<i>Type/Location</i>							
<i>Notes</i>							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Secondary Enabler</td> <td>Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Secondary Enabler	Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery	<i>Type/Location</i>		<i>Notes</i>	
Secondary Enabler	Low-Latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery						
<i>Type/Location</i>							
<i>Notes</i>							
Hardware/Software requirements:							
Similar to UC3.3_SC6							
Additional information:							

Use Case 4.1 Test Cases

Table 46: Use Case 4.1 Trials.

Environment ID	TER
UC ID:	4.1
Title:	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go
UC Owner:	Brainstorm
UC Scenarios Description	

UC Scenario List:			
<p>TER: The scenarios listed below have the scope to progressively adapt the developed software solution to the 5G mobile technology and its improved network features. First the virtualized service should be deployed in a domain and tested in a lab environment (CTTC) to verify that all the interactions between clients, service and enablers are working properly. The same solution will be then tested in Tallin (TTU) deploying it in one of the systems that will be employed for the field trials. These testing operations will lead to a final and fully capable system that support all the enablers and clients' interactions. After this phase, the solution will be tested in field trials: first in simplified settings where just a client will cross the border and its service re instantiated in the visiting domain. After this simplified attempt and the optimizations due to its results the system will be then tested in real settings, serving several clients (>2). These clients will be moving across the border onboarded on the cars employed for terrestrial use cases, replicating a real collaborative game situation involving several users that will cross the border at the same time. This will allow to verify how the client application and service are affected during network operator transition.</p>			
ID	Testing Environment	Location	Class type
TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1	Terrestrial	CTTC	URLLC
TER_UC4.1_LT2_SC1	Terrestrial	Tallin	URLLC
TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC

Table 47: TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1	CTTC	URLCC(M)	Not applies
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		5	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the system over a 5G network at CTTC testbed facility. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in order to simulate the cross-border operations in lab environment.			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate service availability and functionalities

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service-related issues

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1_TO3
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify the clients-enablers interactions

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1_TO4
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check simulated cross border issues with simplified scenario (1 user).

Target KPIs & Measurements:

In this prototype verification context, NO KPIs will be recorded and uploaded as results to the TWP. The scope of this test case is to verify that all the components involved in the tested system are properly interacting. The verification will allow to adjust the application configuration and the connected service to the project's specific infrastructure, to obtain a first functional system working properly with enablers and clients and collecting the KPIs.

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	CTTC
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Testbed tools and access (devices, one k8s for each domain, etc.)

Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the collaborative game client application and client movement simulation script on a test device; Deploy the virtualized service in the CAM repository; Carry out the cross-border simulation emitting simulated GPS coordinates to the V2X and verifying that all the

	enablers fulfil with their functions and provide the correct data to the client.
Primary User/Actor	CTTC
Tasks	Provide 5G testbed, VMs to monitor and simulate, remote access to systems in the lab environment.
Pre-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Linux/Win machine with Python 9. GPS track loaded and simulation script ready to run. 10. Game service deployed at the cam services repo. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 22. Operator starts the Experiment in the TWP 23. Operator start the client simulation script on test device 24. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients via IF. 25. Application connects to the service and the gaming session starts properly. 26. GPS simulation starts, CAM messages sent to the V2X broker. 27. Approaching the border, the infrastructure should deploy a new service in the visiting domain (PRAE + IF). 28. Visiting domain service details, communicated to the clients (ASC + v2X + IF) 29. Disconnection simulation (VPN drop) 30. Reconnection simulation 	
Post-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain. 2. Gaming session re established properly. 3. Clients messages are received properly by the v2X Broker In the visiting domain 	
Technical Enablers requirements:	

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Store service Image and deployment settings
Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Allow intercommunication between all the infrastructure components, clients and services
Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Start/Stop experiment. Save the experimental results.
Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Process the intercommunication of enablers, services, clients
Secondary Enabler	Assisted service continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Provide data on the new instantiated services for the cross-border operations
Secondary Enabler	Proactive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Trigger the IF when the clients(leader) are approaching the border
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Game service. Virtualized on CTTC k8s cluster, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and updating all connected clients accordingly. ● Linux/win computer to run the simulation (include machine's OS version of client app), will display last game scene updated from the game service. 	
Additional information:	
This test will not employ 5G radio connection.	

Table 48: TER_UC4.1_LT2_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.1_LT2_SC1	TTU	URLCC(M)	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		5	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
<p>The differences with respect the scenario described previously (TER_UC4.1_LT1_SC1) are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that the test will be carried out at TTU premises, installing the services in the CAM repository deployment that will be employed during the field trials. - The client application version tested will be the final one. All the interactions and messaging, previously (reference Scenario) carried out employing the python simulation script, will be implemented in the Android application that will be employed for the field trials. - The Android application will run on a 5G SA compatible device. 			

Table 49: TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Valka-Valga	URLCC(M)	Stand Alone (Rel. ??)
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		10	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
<p>Test the system in field settings. The user involved in the test will be onboarded on one of cars provided by the CCAM use cases. The car will then travel along the programmed route and cross the border between the instrumented smart crossings in Valga and Valka. The user will play the collaborative game during the travel.</p>			

Test Objective(s):	
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test cross boarder operations with simplified scenario (1 user).
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify service reconnection and related application functions after Operator transition.
KPIs & Measurements:	
The test repetitions will allow to generate KPIs measurements (time series). They will be recorded employing TWP compatible files (CSV) and uploaded after every test repetition.	
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	Brainstorm
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the collaborative game client application on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	EDI, VTT
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide transport to Infotainment users for crossing the border.
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	TTU, LMT, TELIA, EEE
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Infrastructure, devices and support for the field trials.
Pre-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Car transportation ready 2. UEs charged and equipped with the proper SIM. 3. Operator monitoring for service readiness. 	

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operator starts the Experiment in the TWP 2. User on car starts the client application on test device. 3. After service deployment, service IP distributed to clients via IF. (Verified by user on car) 4. Application connects to the service (Verified by operator) 5. Gaming session starts properly. (Verified by user on car) 6. Car starts moving, CAM messages sent to the V2X broker by the gaming app. (Verified by operator) (Comparison with car positioning if system is also started) 7. Approaching the border, the infrastructure should deploy a new service in the visiting domain (PRAE + IF). (Verified by operator) 8. Visiting domain service details, communicated to the clients via IF (ASC + v2X + IF) (Verified by user on car) 9. the car crosses the border that divides the coverage of the two networks involved. (Verified by user on car and operator) 10. Domain change due to network provider transition. (Verified by operator) 11. Gaming app status monitoring while user is playing (by user on car) 12. Connection to the visiting domain service established (Verified by user on car and operator) 13. Gaming user follows playing, resuming the session properly 							
Post-Conditions:							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain. 2. Gaming session re established properly. 3. Clients messages are received properly by the v2X Broker In the visiting domain 							
Technical Enablers requirements:							
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 30%;">Primary Enabler</td> <td>Cam Repository</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type/Location</td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Notes</td> <td>Store service Image and deployment settings</td> </tr> </table>		Primary Enabler	Cam Repository	Type/Location	CTTC	Notes	Store service Image and deployment settings
Primary Enabler	Cam Repository						
Type/Location	CTTC						
Notes	Store service Image and deployment settings						

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Allow intercommunication between all the infrastructure components, clients and services
Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Start/Stop experiment. Save the experimental results.
Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Process the intercommunication of enablers, services, clients
Secondary Enabler	Assisted service continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Provide data on the new instantiated services for the cross border operations
Secondary Enabler	Proactive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Trigger the IF when the clients(leader) are approaching the border
Hardware/Software requirements:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Game service. Deployed on TTU k8s cluster, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and updating all connected clients accordingly. ● 5G SA compatible Android device. to run the gaming app, will display last game scene updated from the game service. ● Laptop for the operator to monitor the gaming app interactions with the different enablers. 	
Additional information:	

Use Case 4.2 Test Cases

Table 50: Use Case 4.2 Trials.

Environment ID	TER			
UC ID:	4.2			
Title:	immersive conferencing tools on the go			
UC Owner:	Brainstorm			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>TER: The scenarios listed below have the scope to progressively adapt the developed software solution to the 5G mobile technology and its improved network features. First the virtualized service should be deployed in a domain and tested in a lab environment (CTTC) to verify that all the interactions between clients, service and enablers are working properly. The same solution will be then tested in Tallin (TTU) deploying it in one of the systems that will be employed for the field trials. These testing operations will lead to a final and fully capable system that support all the enablers and clients' interactions. After this phase, the solution will be tested in field trials: first in simplified settings where just a client will cross the border and its service re instantiated in the visiting domain. After this simplified attempt and the optimizations due to its results the system will be then tested in real settings, serving a number of clients superior to two. These clients will be moving across the border onboarded on the cars employed for terrestrial use cases, replicating a real collaborative VR situation involving several users that will cross the border at the same time. This will allow to verify how the client VR Player and service are affected during network operator transition.</p>				
	ID	Testing Environment	Location	Class type
	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1	Terrestrial	CTTC	URLLC
	TER_UC4.2_LT2_SC1	Terrestrial	Tallin	URLLC
	TER_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Terrestrial	Valka/Valga	URLLC

Table 51: TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1	CTTC	URLCC(M)	Not applies
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		5	

Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):					
No Proceed					
Brief description of the UC Scenario:					
Test the system over a 5G network at CTTC testbed facility. Verify and adjust VR Player and connected service features in order to simulate the cross border operations in lab environment.					
Test Objective(s):					
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Validate service availability and functionalities</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate service availability and functionalities
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO1				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate service availability and functionalities				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Find and fix virtualized service-related issues</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service-related issues
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO2				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Find and fix virtualized service-related issues				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO3</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Verify the clients-enablers interactions</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO3	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify the clients-enablers interactions
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO3				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify the clients-enablers interactions				
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO4</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Check simulated cross boarder issues with simplified scenario (1 user).</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO4	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check simulated cross boarder issues with simplified scenario (1 user).
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1_TO4				
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Check simulated cross boarder issues with simplified scenario (1 user).				
Target KPIs & Measurements:					
In this prototype verification context, <u>NO KPIs will be recorded and uploaded as results to the TWP</u> . The scope of this test case is to verify that all the components involved in the tested system are properly interacting. The verification will allow to adjust the VR Player configuration and the connected service to the project's specific infrastructure, to obtain a first functional system working properly with enablers and clients and collecting the KPIs.					
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:					

Primary User/Actor	CTTC
Tasks	Provide 5G Testbed tools and access (devices, one k8s for each domain, etc.)

Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm
Tasks	Deploy the VR Player and client movement simulation script on a test device; Deploy the virtualized service in the CAM repository; Carry out the cross border simulation emitting simulated GPS coordinates to the V2X and verifying that all the enablers fulfil with their functions and provide the correct data to the client.

Primary User/Actor	CTTC
Tasks	Provide 5G testbed, VM to simulate the emission point and to monitor the service, remote access to systems in the lab environment.

Pre-Conditions:

11. Linux/Win machine with Python
12. GPS track loaded and simulation script ready to run.
13. VR service deployed at the cam services repo.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

31. Operator starts the Experiment in the TWP
32. Operator start the client simulation script on test device
33. After service deployment, service IP is distributed to clients via IF.
34. VR Player connects to the service and VR conferencing session starts properly.
35. GPS simulation starts, CAM messages sent to the V2X broker.
36. Approaching the border, the infrastructure should deploy a new service in the visiting domain (PRAE + IF).
37. Visiting domain service details, communicated to the clients (ASC + v2X + IF)

38. Disconnection simulation (VPN drop)

39. Reconnection simulation

Post-Conditions:

1. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain.
2. VR Conferencing session re established properly.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Store service Image and deployment settings

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Allow intercommunication between all the infrastructure components, clients and services

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Start/Stop experiment. Save the experimental results.

Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Process the intercommunication of enablers, services, clients

Secondary Enabler	Assisted service continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Provide data on the new instantiated services for the cross-border operations

Secondary Enabler	Proactive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	CTTC
<i>Notes</i>	Trigger the IF when the clients(leader) are approaching the border

Hardware/Software requirements:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VR service. Virtualized on CTTC k8s cluster, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the VR and updating all connected clients accordingly. • Linux/win computer to run the simulation (include machine's OS version of client app), will display last VR scene updated from the VR service.
Additional information:
This test will not employ 5G radio connection.

Table 52: TER_UC4.2_LT2_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.2_LT2_SC1	TTU	URLCC(M)	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		5	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
<p>The differences with respect the scenario described previously (TER_UC4.2_LT1_SC1) are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - that the test will be carried out at TTU premises, installing the services in the CAM repository deployment that will be employed during the field trials. - The VR Player version tested will be the final one. All the interactions and messaging, previously (reference Scenario) carried out employing the python simulation script, will be implemented in the VR Player application that will be employed for the field trials. - VR Player will run on a high end laptop for gaming 			

Table 53: TER_UC4.2_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
TER_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Valka-Valga	URLCC(M)	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	

Testing Environment	Terrestrial
Number of repetitions	10
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):	
No Proceed	
Brief description of the UC Scenario:	
Test the system in field settings. The user involved in the test will be on boarded on one of cars provided by the CCAM use cases. The car will then travel along the programmed route and cross the border between the instrumented smart crossings in Valga and Valka. The user will join the VR conferencing session during the travel.	
Test Objective(s):	
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_SC1_FT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test cross boarder operations with simplified scenario (1 user).
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	TER_UC4.2_SC1_FT1_TO2
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify service reconnection and related VR Player functions after Operator transition.
KPIs & Measurements:	
The test repetitions will allow to generate KPIs measurements (time series). They will be recorded employing TWP compatible files (CSV) and uploaded after every test repetition.	
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm
Tasks	Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the VR Player on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.
Primary User/Actor	EDI, VTT

<i>Tasks</i>	Provide transport to Infotainment users for crossing the border.
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	TTU, LMT, TELIA, EEE
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide 5G Infrastructure, devices and support for the field trials.
Pre-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Car transportation ready 5. CPE/Dongle connected to the laptop/inverter and equipped with the proper SIM. 6. Laptop/VR headsets connected (inverter/laptop) 7. Operator monitoring for service readiness. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. Operator starts the Experiment in the TWP 15. User on car starts the VR Player on laptop. 16. After service deployment, service IP distributed to clients via IF. (Verified by user on car) 17. VR Player connects to the service (Verified by operator) 18. VR Conferencing session starts properly. (Verified by user on car) 19. Car starts moving, CAM messages sent to the V2X broker by the VR Conferencing app. (Verified by operator) (Comparison with car positioning if system is also started) 20. Approaching the border, the infrastructure should deploy a new service in the visiting domain (PRAE + IF). (Verified by operator) 21. Visiting domain service details, communicated to the clients via IF (ASC + v2X + IF) (Verified by user on car) 22. the car crosses the border that divides the coverage of the two networks involved. (Verified by user on car and operator) 23. Domain change due to network provider transition. (Verified by operator) 24. VR Conferencing app status monitoring while user is viewing the content (by user on car) 25. Connection to the visiting domain service established (Verified by user on car and by operator remotely) 26. VR Conferencing user resumes the VR conferencing session properly 	
Post-Conditions:	

1. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain.
2. VR Conferencing session re established properly.
3. Clients messages are received properly by the v2X Broker In the visiting domain

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Cam Repository
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Store service Image and deployment settings

Secondary Enabler	V2X Broker
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Allow intercommunication between all the infrastructure components, clients and services

Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Start/Stop experiment. Save the experimental results.

Secondary Enabler	Integration Fabric/ Service adapter
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Process the intercommunication of enablers, services, clients

Secondary Enabler	Assisted service continuity
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Provide data on the new instantiated services for the cross border operations

Secondary Enabler	Proactive Resource Allocation
<i>Type/Location</i>	TTU
<i>Notes</i>	Trigger the IF when the clients(leader) are approaching the border

Hardware/Software requirements:

- VR service. Deployed on TTU k8s cluster, in charge of receiving the emission signal and multicast it to the VR players from the edge.
- 5G SA compatible modem (CPE or dongle). To connect the laptop hosting the VR Conferencing app.

- Laptops + VR Headsets
- Laptop for the operator to monitor the VR Conferencing app interactions with the different enablers.

Additional information:

Annex II – Maritime Test Cases

Use Case 4.1 Test Cases

Table 54: Use Case 4.1 Trials.

Environment ID	MAR			
UC ID:	4.1			
Title:	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go			
UC Owner:	Brainstorm			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>The Maritime environment infrastructure differs completely from the terrestrial. This condition obliges to completely modify the service management. In this environment, the service will be onboarded on the mobile cores deployed on the ships. and its function will be measuring the client's interruption time when the connection drops until the following connectivity fall back solution re-establish connectivity to the clients UEs.</p>				
	<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Environment</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>
	MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC
	MAR_UC4.1_FT2_SC1	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC

Table 55: MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
MAR_UC4.1_LT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago	URLCC(M)	NSA + SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Maritime	
Number of repetitions		5	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			

Brief description of the UC Scenario:									
<p>Test the system over a 5G multi-hop network infrastructure deployed on 2 vessels. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in the first infrastructure prototype. Collect KPI continuously to assess the service interruptions effects, from a network point of view, when the multi-hop connectivity management switch the provider from a system to other.</p>									
Test Objective(s):									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Test multi-hop infrastructure with simplified scenario (1 ship and 1 client).</td> </tr> </table> <table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Verify service reconnection and related application functions after connectivity provider transition.</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test multi-hop infrastructure with simplified scenario (1 ship and 1 client).	<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify service reconnection and related application functions after connectivity provider transition.
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test multi-hop infrastructure with simplified scenario (1 ship and 1 client).								
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.1_SC1_FT1_TO2								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify service reconnection and related application functions after connectivity provider transition.								
Target KPIs & Measurements:									
<p>The test repetitions will allow to generate KPIs measurements (time series). They will be recorded employing TWP compatible files (CSV) and uploaded after every test repetition or at the end of the experimental session (maybe TWP not available in maritime infra)</p>									
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>Brainstorm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the collaborative game client application on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.</td> </tr> </table> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>First Ship</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Provide transport to Infotainment users on the sea.</td> </tr> </table>		Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm	Tasks	Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the collaborative game client application on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.	Primary User/Actor	First Ship	Tasks	Provide transport to Infotainment users on the sea.
Primary User/Actor	Brainstorm								
Tasks	Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the collaborative game client application on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.								
Primary User/Actor	First Ship								
Tasks	Provide transport to Infotainment users on the sea.								

Primary User/Actor	VTT, AIRBUS, DIGITA.
Tasks	Provide Multi-hop 5G Infrastructure, devices and support for the maritime field trials.
Pre-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maritime transportation ready 2. UEs charged and equipped with the proper SIM. 3. Operator monitoring for service readiness. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Operator starts the Experiment in the TWP 2. User starts the client application on test device. 3. Application connects to the service (Verified by operator) 4. Gaming session starts properly. (Verified by user) 5. connectivity provider transition. (Verified by operator) 6. Gaming app status monitoring while user is playing (by user) 7. Re connection to the service through the new connectivity provider (Verified by user and operator) 8. Gaming user follows playing, resuming the session properly (Verified by user) 	
Post-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain. 4. Gaming session re established properly. 5. Clients messages are received properly by the v2X Broker In the visiting domain 	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal
Type/Location	CTTC
Notes	Save the experimental results.
Hardware/Software requirements:	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Game service. Installed on portable 5G core deployed on the ship, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and updating all connected clients accordingly. ● 5G SA compatible Android device. to run the gaming app, will display last game scene updated from the game service. ● Laptop for the operator to monitor the gaming app interactions with its service installed in the core.
Additional information:

Table 56: MAR_UC4.1_FT2_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
MAR_UC4.1_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago	URLCC(M)	NSA + SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Terrestrial	
Number of repetitions		10	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
The differences with respect the scenario described previously (MAR_UC4.1_FT1_SC1) are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The test will be carried out employing more than one ship to support the multi-hop infrastructure. - The number of clients involved to test the infrastructure will be increased (>2). 			

Use Case 4.2 Test Cases

Table 57: Use Case 4.2 Trials.

Environment ID	MAR
UC ID:	4.2
Title:	VR Conferencing on the go.
UC Owner:	Brainstorm
UC Scenarios Description	
UC Scenario List:	

The Maritime environment infrastructure differs completely from the terrestrial. This condition obliges to completely modify the service management. In this environment, the service will be onboarded on the mobile cores deployed on the ships. and its function will be measuring the client's interruption time when the connection drops until the following connectivity fall back solution re-establish connectivity to the clients UEs.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Testing Environment</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>
MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC
MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1	Maritime	Turku Archipelago	URLLC

Table 58: MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago	URLCC(M)	NSA + SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		No Proceed	
Testing Environment		Maritime	
Number of repetitions		5	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Test the system over a 5G multi-hop network infrastructure deployed on a ship and other support ship. Verify and adjust application and connected service features in the first infrastructure prototype. Collect KPI continuously to assess the service interruptions effects, from a network point of view, when the multi-hop connectivity management switch the provider from a system to other.			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.2_SC1_FT1_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test multi-hop infrastructure with simplified scenario (1 ship and 1 client).		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC4.2_SC1_FT1_TO2		

<i>Test Objective:</i>	Verify service reconnection and related application functions after connectivity provider transition.
Target KPIs & Measurements:	
The test repetitions will allow to generate KPIs measurements (time series). They will be recorded employing TWP compatible files (CSV) and uploaded after every test repetition or at the end of the experimental session (maybe TWP not available in maritime infra)	
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	Brainstorm
<i>Tasks</i>	Deploy the containerized service in the CAM repository; Install and configure the collaborative game client application on test devices; monitor and support the system during the trials; collect KPIs measurements files from devices and upload to the TWP.
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	First ship
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide transport to Infotainment users on the sea.
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	VTT, AIRBUS, CUMUCORE.
<i>Tasks</i>	Provide Multi-hop 5G Infrastructure, devices and support for the maritime field trials.
Pre-Conditions:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maritime transportation ready 2. UEs charged and equipped with the proper SIM. 3. Operator monitoring for service readiness. 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. User starts the client application on test device. 5. Application connects to the service (Verified by operator) 	

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Gaming session starts properly. (Verified by user) 7. connectivity provider transition. (Verified by operator) 8. Gaming app status monitoring while user is playing (by user) 9. Re connection to the service through the new connectivity provider (Verified by user and operator) 10. Gaming user follows playing, resuming the session properly (Verified by user) 						
Post-Conditions:						
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once re-connected, clients should connect to the service deployed in the visiting domain. 2. VR session re established properly. 						
Technical Enablers requirements:						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Secondary Enabler</td> <td>Tenant Web Portal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Type/Location</td> <td>CTTC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Notes</td> <td>Save the experimental results.</td> </tr> </table>	Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal	Type/Location	CTTC	Notes	Save the experimental results.
Secondary Enabler	Tenant Web Portal					
Type/Location	CTTC					
Notes	Save the experimental results.					
Hardware/Software requirements:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VR Video streaming source. Installed on portable 5G core deployed on the ship, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and updating all connected clients accordingly. ● 5G SA compatible Android device. To use as 5G modem, attached to VR headset. ● Laptop for the operator to run the VR player that is connecting to the VR Video streaming source. 						
Additional information:						

Table 59: MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA
MAR_UC4.2_FT2_SC1	Turku Archipelago	URLCC(M)	NSA + SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1	
Testing Environment		Maritime	

Number of repetitions	10
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):	
The differences with respect the scenario described previously (MAR_UC4.2_FT1_SC1) are:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The test will be carried out employing more than one ship to support the multi-hop infrastructure. - The number of clients involved to test the infrastructure will be increased (>2). 	

Use Case 5.1 Test Cases

Table 60: Use Case 5.1 Trials.

Environment ID:	Maritime			
UC ID:	UC 5.1			
Title:	Connected Logistics			
UC Owner:	Vedia			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.</p> <p>Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, i.e., transportation needs to be monitored continuously via a remote-control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity.</p> <p>Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard devices, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.</p> <p>All testing is first started in lab environment and after successful results tests are moved to outside, first in land and finally in maritime environment. When all pre-testing is accepted outside trials will be moved to actual trial environment in the Archipelago of Turku Finland.</p>				
<i>ID</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
MAR_UC5.1_SC1_LT1	Lab test	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_SC2_FT1	Field trial	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_SC3_FT2	Field test	Turku Archipelago Sea (Ferry)	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA

MAR_UC5.1_SC4_FT3	Field test	Turku (Ferry)	Archipelago	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.1_SC5_FT4	Field trial	Turku (Ferry)	Archipelago	URLCC	NSA + SA

Table 61: MAR_UC5.1_SC1_LT1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
MAR_UC5.1_SC1_LT1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA (Commercial NSA)
Testing Environment:		Testing done in VTT (Espoo) lab premises.	
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		NA	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
NA			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Lab test for test system interoperability and applications.			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.1_SC1_LT1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate trial setup and system interoperability in Cumuore 5G core environment.		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity		
<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
Primary User/Actor	Vedia		
Tasks	System and application testing		
Primary User/Actor	Cumuore		

<i>Tasks</i>	Access to test network and SIM cards												
<i>Other User/Actor</i>	VTT												
<i>Tasks</i>	Support for data collection and access to test network												
Pre-Conditions:													
VTT and Cumucore will enable test environment for the VTT lab													
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:													
VTT and Cumucore will setup test environment, which later on will be tested with Vedia test devices.													
Post-Conditions:													
After testing, necessary adjustments will be done and if needed the test will be repeated again. After positive test results trial will be repeated outside.													
Technical Enablers requirements:													
<p>Test must be done in 5G test network.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary Enabler</i></td> <td>5G SA test network</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>Espoo / Finland</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td>Cumucore test networks</td> </tr> </table> <table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Secondary Enabler</i></td> <td>VTT data collection and analysis</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>Espoo / Finland</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td>VTT test networks</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Primary Enabler</i>	5G SA test network	<i>Type/Location</i>	Espoo / Finland	<i>Notes</i>	Cumucore test networks	<i>Secondary Enabler</i>	VTT data collection and analysis	<i>Type/Location</i>	Espoo / Finland	<i>Notes</i>	VTT test networks
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	5G SA test network												
<i>Type/Location</i>	Espoo / Finland												
<i>Notes</i>	Cumucore test networks												
<i>Secondary Enabler</i>	VTT data collection and analysis												
<i>Type/Location</i>	Espoo / Finland												
<i>Notes</i>	VTT test networks												
Hardware/Software requirements:													
5G test network, terminals (5G radio) and Vedia test devices													
Additional information:													
VTT support for configuring test devices to test networks, IoT data source – RTK assistance data solution.													

Table 62: MAR.UC5.1_SC2_FT1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:						
MAR.UC5.1_SC2_FT1	Espoo/Finland	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA (commercial NSA)						
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR.UC5.1_SC1_LT1							
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):									
MAR.UC5.1_SC2_FT1 will follow MAR.UC5.1_SC1_LT1 and its outcomes and findings									
Brief description of the UC Scenario:									
Pre-testing for actual maritime trials. Replication of first lab trials, but outside and with moving vehicles									
Test Objective(s):									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Validate trial setup and system interoperability in Cumuore 5G core environment with moving vehicle.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate trial setup and system interoperability in Cumuore 5G core environment with moving vehicle.		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO1								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate trial setup and system interoperability in Cumuore 5G core environment with moving vehicle.								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Load and throughput capacity</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Load and throughput capacity		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1SC2FT1_TO2								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Load and throughput capacity								
Target KPIs & Measurements:									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>Connectivity</td> <td>Number of devices per cell per MHz</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz	<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.	
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz							
<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.								
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>Vedia</td> <td>Vedia</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>System and application testing</td> <td>mMTC test</td> </tr> </table>				Primary User/Actor	Vedia	Vedia	Tasks	System and application testing	mMTC test
Primary User/Actor	Vedia	Vedia							
Tasks	System and application testing	mMTC test							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Primary User/Actor</td> <td>Cumuore</td> <td>Taltech</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tasks</td> <td>Access to test network and SIM cards</td> <td>Support, access to test network and SIM cards</td> </tr> </table>				Primary User/Actor	Cumuore	Taltech	Tasks	Access to test network and SIM cards	Support, access to test network and SIM cards
Primary User/Actor	Cumuore	Taltech							
Tasks	Access to test network and SIM cards	Support, access to test network and SIM cards							

Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Support for data collection and access to test network
Other User/Actor	Airbus
Tasks	Satellite connection
Other User/Actor	Digita
Tasks	Support for connectivity and access
Pre-Conditions:	
MAR.UC5.1_SC1_LT1 must prove that test system works and data exchange connection is achieved. 5G SA core must be enabled and 5G network available.	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
Based on the outcomes from MAR.UC5.1_SC1_LT1 this scenario will continue field trials preparations. Aim is to repeat the lab test, but now outside and with the moving vehicles. The whole test setup will be tested and tests must be passed before moving on the real trial site in the maritime environment.	
Post-Conditions:	
5G test network and devices with RTK assistance data transmission service have been tested and system is accepted. Test group can receive and collect necessary data for KPIs. Test can be continued in the real test environment.	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	5G test network
Type/Location	NSA (commercial) + SA / Espoo/Otaniemi (Finland)
Notes	Outside test network environment
Secondary Enabler	Test setup devices and software are working and interoperable
Type/Location	Vedia devices and third-party data analysis tools / physical and cloud services
Notes	Dedicated KPIs can be monitored and data for those is available
Hardware/Software requirements:	
5G NSA + SA test network, terminals (5G radio) and Vedia test devices, Vedia Enide interface	
Additional information:	
Cumucore/Digita/VTT support for configuring test devices to test networks, IoT data source – RTK assistance data solution.	

Table 63: MAR.UC5.1_FT2_SC3 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:						
MAR.UC5.1_FT2_SC3	Turku Archipelago	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA						
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR.UC5.1_FT3_SC5 and MAR.UC5.1_FT4_SC5							
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):									
One vessel/boat trial, before moving on more challenging two vessel scenario.									
Brief description of the UC Scenario:									
Connectivity and system setup testing in maritime environment with one vessel/boat. Aim is to test connectivity and quality of service in the sea.									
Test Objective(s):									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>5G (NSA) network from the shore and on vessel SA network</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	5G (NSA) network from the shore and on vessel SA network		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO1								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	5G (NSA) network from the shore and on vessel SA network								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Satellite backhaul for 5G</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Satellite backhaul for 5G		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO2								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Satellite backhaul for 5G								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO3</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO3	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2_TO3								
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability								
Target KPIs & Measurements:									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>Connectivity</td> <td>Number of devices per cell per MHz</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz	<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.	
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz							
<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored.								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Secondary KPI:</i></td> <td>Coverage</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td>Basic coverage in maritime environment</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Coverage		<i>Measurements:</i>	Basic coverage in maritime environment	
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Coverage								
<i>Measurements:</i>	Basic coverage in maritime environment								

<i>Tertiary KPI:</i>	Average throughput	
<i>Measurements:</i>	Data throughput capacity	
<i>Fourth KPI:</i>	Positioning error (m)	
<i>Measurements:</i>	RTK positioning accuracy	
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:		
Primary User/Actor	Vedia	Vedia
Tasks	System and application testing	mMTC test
Primary User/Actor	Cumucore	Taltech
Tasks	Access to 5G test network and SIM cards	Support, access to test network and SIM cards
Other User/Actor	VTT	
Tasks	Support for data collection and access to test network	
Other User/Actor	Airbus	
Tasks	Satellite connection	
Other User/Actor	Digita	
Tasks	Support for connectivity and access	
Other User/Actor	Turku University of Applied Science	
Tasks	Test vessel availability and operation at the coast	
Pre-Conditions:		
5G network and satellite backhaul are implemented to the vessel, which is offered as test platform. All test devices can be integrated to vessel test setup.		
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:		

- A) 5G (NSA + SA) network and satellite backhaul are planned and implemented to vessel
- B) devices are tested on vessel
- C) results are analyzed against KPIs
- D) test is repeated if necessary

Post-Conditions:

5G (NSA + SA) network and devices with satellite backhaul data transmission service running within targeted KPIs until removed after testing. Use case is ready to be tested in two vessel scenarios, i.e. multi-hop connection can be added to the tests.

Technical Enablers requirements:

Primary Enabler	Satellite backhaul service, antenna and receiver on the vessel
<i>Type/Location</i>	low orbit satellite constellation/Baltic sea
<i>Notes</i>	Airbus service

Secondary Enabler	5G test network and devices
<i>Type/Location</i>	SA connection for trial site
<i>Notes</i>	Cumocore/VTT/Digita/Telia service

Hardware/Software requirements:

Satellite antenna and receiver connected to on vessel communication infra, 5G test devices and -equipment

Additional information:

Cumucore/Digita/VTT support for configuring test devices to test networks, IoT data source – RTK assistance data solution.

Table 64: MAR.UC5.1_FT3_SC4 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:								
MAR.UC5.1_FT3_SC4	Turku archipelago	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA								
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR.UC5.1_SC5_FT2 and MAR.UC5.1_SC5_FT4									
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):											
Two vessel test scenario, i.e multihop connection from vessel to vessel											
Brief description of the UC Scenario:											
Connectivity and system setup testing in maritime environment with two vessels. Aim is to test connectivity and quality of service in the sea and focus on multi-hop connection between the vessels.											
Test Objective(s):											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td colspan="3">MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td colspan="3">Multihop connection between vessels</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO1			<i>Test Objective:</i>	Multihop connection between vessels		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO1										
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Multihop connection between vessels										
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td colspan="3">MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td colspan="3">Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO2			<i>Test Objective:</i>	Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO2										
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Ensure functionality of the devices and test system interoperability										
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td colspan="3">MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO3</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td colspan="3">KPI measurements from both vessels</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO3			<i>Test Objective:</i>	KPI measurements from both vessels		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3_TO3										
<i>Test Objective:</i>	KPI measurements from both vessels										
Target KPIs & Measurements:											
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary KPI:</i></td> <td>Connectivity</td> <td>Number of devices per cell per MHz</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td colspan="2">technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored via multi-hop connection.</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz	<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored via multi-hop connection.			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Connectivity	Number of devices per cell per MHz									
<i>Measurements:</i>	technical interoperability is achieved and data can be shared and stored via multi-hop connection.										
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Secondary KPI:</i></td> <td colspan="3">Coverage</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Measurements:</i></td> <td colspan="3">Coverage for multi-hop connection, including max distance</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Coverage			<i>Measurements:</i>	Coverage for multi-hop connection, including max distance		
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Coverage										
<i>Measurements:</i>	Coverage for multi-hop connection, including max distance										

<i>Tertiary KPI:</i>	KPIs measurements
<i>Measurements:</i>	technical testing for pre-set KPIs

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	Vedia	Vedia
Tasks	System and application testing	mMTC test

Primary User/Actor	Cumucore	Taltech
Tasks	Access to test network and SIM cards	Support, access to test network and SIM cards

Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Support for data collection and access to test network

Other User/Actor	Digita
Tasks	Support for connectivity and access

Other User/Actor	West coast SeaServices – vessel 1
Tasks	Vessel availability and access

Other User/Actor	West coast SeaServices -vessel 2
Tasks	Vessel availability and operation at sea

Pre-Conditions:

Successful lab tests for multi-hop connection. Both test vessels are equipped with necessary devices and communication capability.

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:

A) multi-hop are planned and implemented to vessels

B) devices are tested on vessel						
C) results are analyzed against KPIs						
D) test is repeated if necessary						
Post-Conditions:						
Multi-hop connection and data transmission service running within targeted kpis until removed after testing.						
Technical Enablers requirements:						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary Enabler</i></td> <td>Multi-hop communication setup implemented into vessels</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>multi-hop connection from vessel to vessel/Turku archipelago</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td>Digita, Cumucore and VTT</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Multi-hop communication setup implemented into vessels	<i>Type/Location</i>	multi-hop connection from vessel to vessel/Turku archipelago	<i>Notes</i>	Digita, Cumucore and VTT
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	Multi-hop communication setup implemented into vessels					
<i>Type/Location</i>	multi-hop connection from vessel to vessel/Turku archipelago					
<i>Notes</i>	Digita, Cumucore and VTT					
Hardware/Software requirements:						
Multi-hop antennas and communication infra implemented in both vessels						
Additional information:						
Cumucore/Digita/VTT support for configuring test devices to test networks						

Table 65: MAR.UC5.1_FT4_SC5 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
MAR.UC5.1_FT4_SC5	Turku archipelago	connectivity/QoS	NSA + SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):	MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2 and MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3		
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
MAR.UC5.1_SC5_FT4 will combine MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2 and MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3 and will work as final test scenario for continuous 5G connectivity for maritime, where all test scenarios are tested and KPIs measured.			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
This test scenario will combine previous test scenarios (MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2 and MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3) and utilize all available connections: from the shore, multi-hop and satellite connection. Aim is to study coverage and quality of connection. These connection alternatives will be tested against KPIs covering both device and network. Aim is to enable continuous connectivity.			
Test Objective(s):			

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC5_FT4_TO1
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Continuous connection to end devices

<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.1_SC5_FT4_TO2	
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Measure KPIs	

Target KPIs & Measurements:

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Service continuity
<i>Measurements:</i>	Coverage, service interruption time, packet error rate, application handover success rate

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Latency
<i>Measurements:</i>	Communication end-to-end latency and user perceived end-to-end latency

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Throughput
<i>Measurements:</i>	Average and min throughput

<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Localization
<i>Measurements:</i>	Position error

Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:

Primary User/Actor	Vedia	Vedia
Tasks	System and application testing	mMTC test

Primary User/Actor	Cumucore	Taltech
Tasks	Access to test network and SIM cards	Support, access to test network and SIM cards

Other User/Actor	VTT
Tasks	Support for data collection and access to test network
Other User/Actor	Digita
Tasks	Support for connectivity and access
Other User/Actor	West Cost SeaServices – Vessel 1
Tasks	Vessel availability and access
Other User/Actor	West Cost SeaServices – Vessel 2
Tasks	Vessel availability and operation at sea
Pre-Conditions:	
MAR.UC5.1_SC3_FT2 and MAR.UC5.1_SC4_FT3 must be finalized and both scenarios must prove required functionalities and pass test scenarios.	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<p>A) 5G (NSA + SA) network, multi-hop and satellite backhaul are tested in vessels</p> <p>B) devices are tested on vessels</p> <p>C) multi-hop connection between vessels enabled</p> <p>D) tests are repeated and data gathered during the cruise</p> <p>D) results are analyzed against KPIs</p> <p>E) test is repeated if necessary</p>	
Post-Conditions:	
KPI measurements for all connectivity alternatives have been accepted	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	Multi-hop communication setup implemented into vessels
Type/Location	multi-hop connection from vessel to vessel/Turku archipelago
Notes	Digita, Cumucore and VTT
Primary Enabler	Satellite backhaul service, antenna and receiver on the vessel
Type/Location	low orbit satellite constellation/Turku archipelago
Notes	Airbus service

Secondary Enabler	5G network and devices
Type/Location	5G from the shore connection for trial site
Notes	Cumocore/VTT/Digita/Telia service
Hardware/Software requirements:	
Satellite antenna and receiver connected to on vessel communication infra, 5G test devices and equipment. Multi-hop antennas and communication infra implemented in both vessels.	
Additional information:	
Final test will be later on repeated in maritime demo, which aims for live demonstration. However, all tests needs to be well documented and videos and pictures are needed to supplement written documentation.	

Use Case 5.2 Test Cases

Table 66: Use Case 5.2 Trials.

Environment ID:	MAR			
UC ID:	UC 5.2			
Title:	Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border			
UC Owner:	WINGS			
UC Scenarios Description				
UC Scenario List:				
<p>This use case aims to provide a continuous video communication with the ferry's staff and also with the harbour's administration to lead to a safe trip for the passengers and also for the cargo that is transported inside the ferry. Lack of communication between the ferry and its staff at a cross border can possibly lead to human fatalities and damage to ferry. It focuses on the provision of live streaming services between the captain and the ferry's staff so that a smooth trip can occur throughout the trip including cross border areas. It offers the ability to cover cross-border issues, including seamless communication of high bandwidth video streaming during the multihop communication between harbour to ferry and between ferry to another ferry and seamless support to the captain throughout the trip.</p> <p>Basic testing will be performed in WINGS lab environment and after their completion tests will be transferred to field trials in the Turku Archipelago.</p>				
<i>ID</i>	<i>Modality</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Class type</i>	<i>NSA/SA</i>
MAR_UC5.2_LT1_SC1	Lab test	WINGS lab	Throughput, service delay, video QoS	

MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1	Field trial	Turku Archipelago (Ferry to harbour)	Throughput, service interruption time at cross border, video QoS	NSA + SA
MAR_UC5.2_FT2_SC2	Field trial	Turku Archipelago (Ferry to Ferry)	Throughput, service interruption time at cross border, video QoS	NSA + SA

Table 67: MAR_UC5.1_LT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
MAR_UC5.1_LT1_SC1	WINGS lab	Throughput, video QoS	NSA + SA
Testing Environment:		Testing in WINGS lab premises	
Number of repetitions		4	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No Proceed			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Lab test to test the video streaming functionality between a server and a terminal.			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.2_LT1_SC1_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Validate trial setup of video streaming between the application server and a terminal in WINGS lab environment.		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			
<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Throughput, service delay		
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:			
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	WINGS		
<i>Tasks</i>	Test the operation of the video streaming from a server hosting the video application to a client in WINGS lab by using a public 5G SA network		
Pre-Conditions:			
NA			

Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:							
- Video streaming is transported from the server to a client							
Post-Conditions:							
no post conditions required							
Technical Enablers requirements:							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Primary Enabler</i></td> <td>5G Ferry Board unit (FBU)</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Type/Location</i></td> <td>WINGS lab</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Notes</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		<i>Primary Enabler</i>	5G Ferry Board unit (FBU)	<i>Type/Location</i>	WINGS lab	<i>Notes</i>	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	5G Ferry Board unit (FBU)						
<i>Type/Location</i>	WINGS lab						
<i>Notes</i>							
Hardware/Software requirements:							
5G public network, terminals (5G radio) and WINGS FBU							

Table 68: MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:				
MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1	Turku Archipelago	Throughput, service interruption time	NSA + SA				
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR.UC5.2_SC1_FT1					
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):							
NA							
Brief description of the UC Scenario:							
Test the application of video streaming between a ferry and a harbour. During the test the throughput and the E2E service delay will be measured.							
Test Objective(s):							
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Deployment of the service in a client at the harbour and test the video streaming between the ferry and the harbour</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO1	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Deployment of the service in a client at the harbour and test the video streaming between the ferry and the harbour
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO1						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Deployment of the service in a client at the harbour and test the video streaming between the ferry and the harbour						
<table border="1"> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective ID:</i></td> <td>MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO2</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Test Objective:</i></td> <td>Test the throughput and service interruption time for a video streaming service at a multi hop environment between two ferries</td> </tr> </table>				<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO2	<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test the throughput and service interruption time for a video streaming service at a multi hop environment between two ferries
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR_UC5.2_FT1_SC1_TO2						
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Test the throughput and service interruption time for a video streaming service at a multi hop environment between two ferries						

Target KPIs & Measurements:	
<p>The KPIs that will be measured are the throughput, service delay and service interruption time through a trip of the ferry at the maritime multi hop environment. The measurements will be taken continuously from the ferry start and test ferry to harbour measurements and at the multi hop environment the tests will be taken between two ferries</p>	
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
Primary User/Actor	WINGS
Tasks	Deployment of the service in a client. The service will run from a WINGS server to the WINGS FBU transmitted through the Digita 5G SA network and then it will play at a client. Measurements of throughput and service interruption time will be taken throughout a trip
Primary User/Actor	FINBO
Tasks	It is a ferry that transports the FBU gateway and is equipped with a 5G SA core network
Other User/Actor	Digita
Tasks	Deploys the 5G SA core network in the ferry
Pre-Conditions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FBU to be installed with a SIM in the ferry and CAM service to be installed in a PC also located in the ferry. - 5G SA network operational in the ferry 	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video streaming starts to play from the server located in the ferry or in the cloud, - Video streaming is transmitted from the server to the FBU, - Video streaming is transmitted to the 5G SA network, - The video application is received from the client located at the harbour 	
Post-Conditions:	
No post conditions required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
Primary Enabler	5G test network
Type/Location	In the ferry and at the harbour
Notes	NA

Secondary Enabler	FBU
Type/Location	5G modem with data collector
Notes	NA

Hardware/Software requirements:

Equipment to be used:

- 1 FBU with SIM and camera to transport the video streaming to the 5G SA network,
- 1 or more client terminals to receive the video streaming application,
- 1 server to host the video application

Table 69: MAR_UC5.2_FT2_SC2 Test Case.

UC Scenario ID:	Location:	Class Type:	NSA/SA:
MAR_UC5.2_FT2_SC2	Gulf of Finland	Throughput, service interruption time	SA
Reference Scenario ID (if proceed):		MAR.UC5.2_SC1_FT1	
Differences with respect the reference Scenario (if proceed):			
No differences			
Brief description of the UC Scenario:			
Video streaming from one ferry to another including a cross border			
Test Objective(s):			
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.2_FT2_SC2_TO1		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Evaluate the seamless connectivity of the video streaming at cross border		
<i>Test Objective ID:</i>	MAR.UC5.2_FT2_SC2_TO2		
<i>Test Objective:</i>	Measure the service interruption time at the cross border		
Target KPIs & Measurements:			

<i>Primary KPI:</i>	Service interruption time
<i>Measurements:</i>	Software to be determined
<i>Secondary KPI:</i>	Throughput
<i>Measurements:</i>	Software to be determined
Critical/crucial tasks to be performed by the different actors (primary, others) as part of the UC Scenario:	
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	WINGS
<i>Tasks</i>	System and application testing
<i>Primary User/Actor</i>	Digita
<i>Tasks</i>	Access of FBU gateway to 5G SA network
Pre-Conditions:	
The FBU to have access to the 5G core network	
Flow of work/activities/task related to the UC Scenario:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video streaming starts to play from the server located in the ferry or in the cloud, - Video streaming is transmitted from the server to the FBU, - Video streaming is transmitted to the 5G SA network, - The video application sent from one ferry to another ferry 	
Post-Conditions:	
no post conditions required	
Technical Enablers requirements:	
<i>Primary Enabler</i>	5G test network
<i>Type/Location</i>	In the ferry and at the harbour
<i>Notes</i>	NA
<i>Secondary Enabler</i>	FBU
<i>Type/Location</i>	5G modem with data collector
<i>Notes</i>	NA

Hardware/Software requirements:
Equipment to be used: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 1 FBU with SIM and camera to transport the video streaming to the 5G SA network,- 1 or more client terminals to receive the video streaming application,- 1 server to host the video application